

Effect of Hydrogen Addition in Natural Gas on Selective Catalytic Reduction of NO_x in Power Plants

Final Report Prepared for the Southern California Gas Company

**Bihter Padak, Sahand Faraji, Kyle Horiuchi, Sogand
Aghamohammadi**

Advanced Power and Energy Program

University of California Irvine

10/30/2025

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of hydrogen blending into natural gas on the selective catalytic reduction (SCR) of NO_x in stationary power applications using a $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ -based commercial SCR catalyst. Results indicate that blending hydrogen up to 100% does not inhibit NO_x conversion, even at high water vapor concentrations (up to 34%) resulting from hydrogen combustion, and an increase in NO_x conversion is observed with hydrogen addition. Lean combustion conditions enhance NO_x conversion due to excess oxygen. While increasing SO_2 concentration (up to 500ppm) reduces SCR activity, 100% hydrogen cases exhibit higher NO_x conversion, showing improved sulfur tolerance due to high water content favoring the formation of surface sulfate species rather than sulfites, enhancing catalyst acidity. The characterization results demonstrated that the SCR activity is closely linked to the nature of ammonia species on the catalyst surface and the surface ammonia species is very dynamic and strongly depends on the reaction environment, especially the presence of water vapor with the population of surface species changing with the water content. The findings demonstrate that SCR units can effectively operate without modification when transitioning to hydrogen–natural gas blends, offering a promising route for decarbonizing stationary power systems without compromising NO_x control performance.

Effect of Hydrogen Addition in Natural Gas on Selective Catalytic Reduction of NO_x in Power Plants – Phase I

1. Introduction

Atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) concentrations continue to rise at an unprecedented rate, reaching a record high of approximately 430 ppm in May 2025, with a 22% increase since 1990 [1]. This alarming trend is not only outpacing the emissions pathways set by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to limit global warming to 1.5°C, but also reflects the fastest annual increase ever recorded, driven by record fossil fuel emissions, reduced uptake by natural sinks, and large-scale wildfires. There is a growing need to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and mitigate climate change to avoid negative environmental and human health impacts [2]. California, as one of the pioneer states in the US to move toward green energy, has passed the assembly bill (AB) 398 under AB 32, which aims to reduce the state's GHG emissions to at least 40% below the 1990 level of emissions by 2030 and to 80% below 1990 levels by 2050 [3, 4]. Replacing pipeline natural gas with hydrogen (H₂), a carbon-free fuel, is one approach to directly reduce CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel burning applications [5]. Hydrogen has great potential as a clean fuel as it can be obtained from renewable sources such as water splitting by electrolysis with solar energy and wind power [6-10], microbial biomass [11], and biomass gasification [12]. Introducing renewable hydrogen into the pipeline would decrease the use of fossil fuels and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. For example, blending up to 20% hydrogen by volume can reduce CO₂ emissions by 6-7% without the need of substantial infrastructure modifications [13, 14]. Hydrogen blending into natural gas has been investigated in recent years, providing important information regarding the effects of hydrogen-natural gas blends on the combustion process, such as emission of pollutants, flame structure, flashback, and ignition delay [5, 15-20]. There have been successful demonstrations of hydrogen blending in power plants, meeting the stack NO_x permit levels. A gas turbine by Mitsubishi Hitachi Power Systems tested with a 30% H₂/70% natural gas blend has produced NO_x emissions similar to a natural gas power plant [21]. A 30% H₂ blend in a Caterpillar industrial natural gas engine achieved post-catalyst NO_x emissions below 0.15 g/kWh during steady operation, meeting U.S. EPA standards [22]. The 3-way catalyst maintained compliance by optimizing the air-fuel equivalence ratio (λ), though higher H₂ blends narrowed the acceptable λ

window by 12%. Moreover, the hydrogen cofiring demonstration at NYPA's Brentwood site successfully tested hydrogen blending levels from 5% to 44% by volume in a gas turbine. The results showed that CO₂ emissions decreased by approximately 14% at 35% hydrogen, following the expected trend with increasing hydrogen content. NO_x levels at the turbine outlet increased with hydrogen, but were effectively controlled by adjusting water injection rates, while CO emissions decreased by up to 88% due to enhanced oxidation from hydrogen combustion. Additionally, the NO₂/NO_x ratio dropped by up to 61%, and combustion dynamics remained stable without adverse effects on turbine operation or hardware integrity. These findings indicate that hydrogen blending can reduce CO₂ emissions while maintaining regulatory compliance and potentially improving CO catalyst performance [23]. While large-scale power plants represent a critical frontier for integrating hydrogen into existing energy systems, the application of hydrogen blending extends beyond industrial settings to everyday energy use in residential contexts. For example, the HyDeploy project at Keele University demonstrated the practical feasibility and environmental compliance of introducing a 20% hydrogen blend into a domestic gas network. This blend reported no significant increase in NO_x emissions from domestic boilers, attributed to optimized burner designs and advanced combustion controls. Emissions remained well within EU EcoDesign limits (≤ 56 mg/kWh), ensuring safe and environmentally responsible operation of household heating systems [24]. However, these previous studies have primarily focused on hydrogen blending levels of up to 44%, leaving the effects of higher hydrogen concentrations largely unclear. With these recent efforts, there is a promising outlook for hydrogen implementation into stationary power applications; however, studies considering how pollution control devices, such as the selective catalytic reduction (SCR) unit for reduction of nitrogen oxides (NO_x), would be affected by the addition of hydrogen fuel are still needed, especially at high hydrogen content levels up to 100%.

Selective catalytic reduction with ammonia (NH₃-SCR) is the state-of-the-art technology for NO_x (NO and NO₂) abatement and is widely utilized in stationary power generation [25]. During the NH₃-SCR process, NO and NO₂ react with NH₃ and get reduced to N₂ through a series of catalytic surface reactions. These reactions are known as the fast (R1), standard (R2), and slow (R3) SCR reactions [26]. Stationary power applications commonly employ commercial SCR

catalysts made of vanadia (V_2O_5) supported on titania (TiO_2) often with molybdenum oxide (MoO_3) or tungsten oxide (WO_3) additives [27, 28], denoted by $V_2O_5-WO_3(MoO_3)/TiO_2$. These catalysts have been observed to exhibit excellent structural stability and NO_x conversion at standard operating temperatures of 300-400 °C [29-31].

Several factors affecting the performance of commercial V_2O_5 -based SCR catalysts, such as temperature, equivalence ratio (Φ), and flue gas composition, have been extensively studied in the literature. Temperature plays a critical role in the performance of SCR systems [32, 33]. The optimal operating range for most commercial SCR catalysts lies between 250°C and 427°C. Below this range, catalytic activity diminishes, resulting in ammonia slip, while temperatures above this range can lead to ammonia oxidation into NO_x , undermining the SCR process [34]. However, studies have shown that high temperatures, around 500°C under dry feed gas conditions, can enhance SCR activity due to favorable ammonium oxidation [35]. Moreover, low-temperature SCR catalysts are being developed to extend the effective operating window down to 180°C, enabling efficient NO_x reduction at lower temperatures [36]. In terms of catalyst stability, research on V_2O_5 -based SCR catalysts indicates that hydrothermal aging does not significantly affect catalytic activity up to 630°C; however, beyond 660°C, a notable loss of BET surface area occurs, leading to reduced de NO_x efficiency [37]. Additionally, vanadia loading levels have a significant impact on NO_x conversion [38], with an optimal V_2O_5 content in the range of 2–5% offering the best performance at elevated temperatures [29, 35].

Equivalence ratio, representing the fuel-to-air ratio, is another parameter that has a great influence on SCR performance. The equivalence ratio can vary from stoichiometric ($\Phi=1$) to a leaner equivalence ratio with excess oxygen ($\Phi=0.5$) depending on the type of stationary power application, such as gas turbines, boilers, gas-fired heaters, and reciprocating engines. The equivalence ratio plays an important role in SCR performance as it determines the amount of excess oxygen present in the flue gas. Oxygen (O_2) is essential for activating the catalyst and promoting the oxidation of NO to NO_2 , which enhances SCR efficiency through the fast SCR

reaction. The SCR reaction in the absence of O₂ has been observed to occur more slowly than the standard SCR reaction [39] since the SCR reaction cannot proceed if the oxygen provided by the catalyst is depleted [40]. Adsorption of NH₃ has been shown to be much stronger in the presence of gas-phase O₂, which is essential for the SCR reaction [41]. Additionally, a kinetic investigation of SCR over a V/Mo/Ti catalyst has shown that increased O₂ content promotes higher NO_x conversion [42]. Increasing the O₂ concentration has been shown to increase the rate of SCR reactions for a V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst [43]. Reaction mechanism studies have identified that O₂ reoxidizes the reduced VO_x sites on the surface [31, 44-47] and the reoxidation of V⁴⁺ by O₂ has been claimed to be a rate-determining step [40]. On the other hand, excessive O₂, particularly at higher temperatures, can lead to the formation of N₂O, a potent greenhouse gas [48]. The optimal O₂ concentration for SCR depends on the catalyst type and reaction conditions, but a moderate level of O₂ is generally preferred to balance reaction efficiency while minimizing unwanted by-products.

In addition to oxygen content in the flue gas, the other components of the flue gas also impact SCR performance. Flue gas from conventional natural gas-fired power plants can contain 8-10% CO₂, 18-20% H₂O, 2-3% O₂, 67-72% N₂, 200-300 ppm CO, 60-280 ppm NO_x and 0.5-4 ppm SO₂ [49-52]. NO_x content in the flue gas depends on several factors including the type of burner that is used in the process, and the NO_x concentration could play a role in the SCR performance. While it is often reported that NO_x conversion over granulated or monolithic catalysts is relatively independent of NO concentration at constant residence time, this relationship does not always hold in powder catalyst reactors [53]. Recent studies have shown that increasing the NO concentration can lead to a noticeable decrease in NO_x conversion in fixed-bed reactors using powdered catalysts. This effect is attributed to mass transfer limitations that become more significant at higher NO levels and lower gas hourly space velocities (GHSV). For example, powdered MnO_x-CeO₂-Al₂O₃ catalysts have been shown to exhibit reduced NO_x conversion efficiency as NO concentration and GHSV increase, highlighting the critical role of diffusion and reactor hydrodynamics in determining catalytic performance under these conditions [54].

SO₂ in the flue gas is known to poison the SCR catalyst through three deactivation processes: deposition of sulfate, competitive adsorption of SO₂, and the oxidation of SO₂ to sulfur

trioxide (SO_3) [55-57]. For supported $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts, in the absence of oxygen in the gas phase, SO_2 has been found to adsorb on TiO_2 as either physisorbed SO_2 or chemisorbed sulfite (SO_3) surface species, and the ratio of the two species depends on the adsorption temperature [58] [59]. In the presence of oxygen, SO_2 can be partially oxidized to SO_3 over $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ -based SCR catalysts [58] on the VO_x sites and the addition of WO_3 decreases the oxidation and increases sulfur resistance [60]. Surface SO_3 species can transform into more stable sulfate (SO_4) species on the surface [61, 62]. If water is present, surface SO_4 species can transform to protonated bidentate surface species [63], which has been shown to increase the surface acidity [62, 64, 65]. On the other hand, SO_3 can react with NH_3 and water and produce ammonium bisulfate or ammonium sulfate [66]. In addition, SO_3 that is released in the gas phase can combine with water vapor to form sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4). Both the ammonium sulfates and sulfuric acid can corrode stainless steel components downstream of the SCR reactor. Therefore, an ideal SCR catalyst must effectively reduce NO_x while minimizing the undesired oxidation of SO_2 to SO_3 [31, 67].

The effect of water content on SCR activity has been found to be both beneficial and inhibitory. The presence of water vapor has been found to increase surface acidity leading to improved adsorption affinity of NH_3 [31, 68]. In contrast, H_2O content between 2.5%-7.5% has been observed to competitively adsorb with NO and NH_3 resulting in decreased SCR activity [69]. In addition to competitive adsorption of water, inhibition of SCR activity in the presence of water has also been attributed to the modification of active sites, such as Lewis acid sites converting to Brønsted acid sites [31, 70-73]. Additionally, some researchers have shown that surface sulfation of the SCR catalyst in the presence of SO_2 and water can improve SCR activity through enhanced acid sites [31, 74]. Despite these studies, the effects of water on vanadia-based SCR catalysts are not fully understood as evidenced by contradictory effects on SCR activity reported in the literature.

Even though these previous studies extensively investigated the factors that impact SCR performance, further studies are needed regarding the role of water in SCR activity [31], especially at high water concentrations. When blending hydrogen into natural gas for stationary power applications, CO_2 emissions would decrease, but the amount of water vapor present in the flue gas would significantly increase up to 34% at a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio. The previous SCR studies reported in the literature did not test high water concentrations that would represent

the flue gas of hydrogen combustion. Given the current interest in blending hydrogen with natural gas for stationary power applications, there is a need to understand how SCR activity would be affected at high water contents provided by hydrogen fuel addition. Therefore, the objective of this study is to understand the effects of hydrogen blending on the NO_x conversion of a V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ commercial SCR catalyst. Additionally, the effects of hydrogen blending on SCR activity with different equivalence ratios, temperatures, and concentrations of NO and SO₂ are also investigated.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Experimental Set-up

A bench-scale quartz packed bed reactor, shown in Figure 1, was used to conduct a series of NH₃-SCR experiments in a simulated flue gas environment representing various stationary power applications. The feed stream to the reactor includes the flue gas components, CO₂, H₂O, N₂ and O₂, SO₂ and NO as well as NH₃ that was added for the SCR reaction. The gas flow rates were regulated by Brooks mass flow controllers, and water vapor was provided via a reciprocating pump (LC-10 AD, Shimadzu), which pumped liquid distilled (DI) water into a stainless-steel evaporator tube heated to 250-300 °C. The quartz reactor was heated using a temperature-controlled Watlow ceramic heater employing National Instrument Control Modules and a PID loop developed within LabVIEW to maintain desired experimental temperatures. The reactor effluent was fed to an in-line particulate filter with a 0.5 μm pore size to capture particles that escaped from the packed bed before the gas was analyzed. Water vapor was condensed and separated from the downstream gas using a thermoelectric gas cooler (ECP1000-SS) and a peristaltic pump (SR25.2-W). The dry gas was then passed through a PG-250 Horiba gas analyzer, where real-time data for NO_x concentration was collected to determine the conversion of NO_x. For reproducibility, the experiments were repeated twice, and the results were reported with a standard deviation error bar to show experimental variability.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental setup.

NH_3 -SCR activity tests were conducted using a V_2O_5 - WO_3 / TiO_2 -based commercial SCR catalyst. The catalyst was initially provided as a monolith and was then crushed and sieved to obtain particle sizes ranging from 250 to 355 μm . For each experiment, 0.71 g SCR catalyst was placed inside the reactor and exposed to a total flow rate of 650 ml/min, resulting in a GHSV of 55,000 [$\text{ml}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]. The influence of various parameters such as temperature and flue gas composition on the SCR performance was investigated. The reactor temperature was varied between 350-400 $^\circ\text{C}$, representing standard operating temperatures used in commercial applications of V_2O_5 -based SCR catalysts. The composition of the simulated flue gas was varied to simulate the combustion of various hydrogen-methane (methane being the largest constituent of natural gas) fuel blends containing 0%-100% H_2 with equivalence ratios between 0.5-0.98 to test different environments experienced in a wide variety of stationary power applications such as gas turbines, boilers, gas-fired heaters, and reciprocating engines. The effect of NO concentration was investigated by introducing 350 ppm and 1000 ppm NO into the reactor. While typical NO_x emissions from stationary power applications are expected to be less than 1000ppm, this concentration was tested to see the impact of increased NO_x levels in case the hydrogen combustion results in a higher level of NO_x concentration. Since the presence of SO_2 is known to

poison the SCR catalysts, the effect of SO₂ was also investigated by introducing 30-500 ppm SO₂ into the reactor. While 30ppm represents a typical SO₂ concentration in the flue gas of natural gas, the higher amounts were tested to simulate longer-term sulfur exposure to study catalyst poisoning in an accelerated manner.

For each experimental run, the flue gas components, CO₂ and O₂, were added upstream of the reactor. Nitrogen was added upstream of the evaporator to act as a carrier gas for the transportation of water vapor into the reactor. The SCR catalyst then underwent hydrothermal aging with the simulated flue gas at 550 °C for 1 hour. Following hydrothermal aging, the temperature was reduced to the desired reaction temperature and after 30 minutes NO, NH₃ and SO₂ (when applicable) were added to begin the experiment. NH₃-SCR experiments were performed for 4-5 hours, and the concentrations of gases were continuously monitored. In addition to the gas analyzer that is used to measure NO_x concentration, the salt method [75-77] was used to measure SO₃ concentration in the gas phase to quantify the amount of SO₃ produced during the experiments. 1 g ultraclean sodium chloride (Sigma Aldrich) was packed in a quartz reactor that is installed downstream of the SCR reactor. The effluent from the SCR reactor was passed through the salt tube, which was kept at 200 °C to prevent water condensation. At this temperature, SO₃ reacts with salt to form sodium sulfate in the presence of water vapor. Sampling time was maintained at 3 hours for all conditions of the NH₃-SCR experiments containing SO₂. The exposed salt sample was then dissolved in 50 ml of DI water and two drops of Thorin indicator solution were added to 10 ml of the dissolved salt sample followed by 40 ml of isopropyl alcohol. Titration with 0.005M Ba(ClO₄)₂ was then performed on the solution until the end point of the reaction as indicated by a color change in the solution from yellow to faded orange. This value represents the amount of SO₃ generated in the reactor and represents the SO₃ concentration present in the salt sample as sulfate.

2.2 Catalyst Characterization

Various characterization methods were used to analyze the SO₂-exposed catalysts. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) were performed with a FEI Magellan 400L XHR SEM operating at 25 kV and 250-50 pA. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) elemental analysis was carried out with an Oxford silicon

drift detector mounted on the Magellan 400L. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed with Kratos Analytical Axis Supra (300W, 20 mA) equipped with a hemispherical electron analyzer, and monochromatic Al-K source was employed to observe the surface chemistry of the SCR catalysts. 160 eV was used to gather survey spectra, while 20 eV and 40 eV were used to obtain high-resolution spectra of elements.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Flue Gas Content

Various simulated flue gas mixtures were tested in the NH₃-SCR experiments to represent a wide range of hydrogen content in the fuel blend. While the CO₂ content of the flue gas decreases with increasing hydrogen, the water vapor concentration increases. With equivalence ratios that are near stoichiometric, the increase in water content with hydrogen addition is larger compared to the leaner equivalence ratios, where the increased water content is offset by excess oxygen. Figure 2a shows the calculated water content of the simulated flue gas as volumetric percentage (vol%), assuming complete combustion, with respect to the hydrogen content in the fuel while the oxygen content (vol%) in the flue gas is shown in Figure 2b. At a constant equivalence ratio, hydrogen addition from 0 to 100% nearly doubles the water content while the oxygen content slightly decreases. The large water content in the flue gas, as high as 34% at a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.98$), is of particular interest for the NH₃-SCR experiments to see the impact of high water content on the catalyst performance that has not been tested before.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. a) Calculated water content (vol%) of the flue gas and b) calculated oxygen content (vol%) of the flue gas for different hydrogen contents in the fuel.

3.2 Effect of Equivalence Ratio and Temperature on NO_x Conversion

As mentioned in the introduction, temperature and the equivalence ratio, representing the fuel/air ratio, play a role in the performance of SCR catalysts. In this study, three different equivalence ratios ($\Phi = 0.5, 0.75, 0.98$) and temperatures ($T = 350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}, 375\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}, 400\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) were tested to see their effect on NO_x conversion. Figure 3 shows NO_x conversion as a function of equivalence ratio for different hydrogen contents (0%-100%) at a temperature of 350 °C and NO concentration of 350 ppm.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Effect of equivalence ratio on NO_x conversion for a) 0% H_2 , b) 20% H_2 , c) 60% H_2 and d) 100% H_2 ($T = 350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{NO} = 350\text{ ppm}$).

In all cases, decreasing the equivalence ratio from 0.98 to 0.5, in other words, increasing the oxygen content of the flue gas from 0.3% to 10%, results in an increase in NO_x conversion. For the fuel-lean mixtures, the presence of excess oxygen in the flue gas could greatly aid the standard SCR reaction (R2). Additionally, excess oxygen may aid the oxidation of some NO into NO_2 , resulting in an increase in the fast SCR reaction (R3) [43]. Oxygen also plays a role in reoxidizing the reduced VO_x sites on the surface [31, 40, 44-47]. All of these contribute to the increase in NO_x conversion as the equivalence ratio is decreased and the excess oxygen in the flue gas increases.

Moreover, the optimal temperature range that commercial vanadia-based SCR catalysts typically operate at (350-400 $^\circ\text{C}$) was tested for different hydrogen contents (0%-100%), at a NO concentration of 350 ppm and two different equivalence ratios, near-stoichiometric (Figure 4) and lean (Figure 5). For the experiments performed at a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.98$), an increase in temperature from 350 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ results in a slight increase in NO_x conversion. At a lean equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.5$), temperature appears to have no significant effect on NO_x conversion; however, the NO_x values are already high due to the presence of excess oxygen at leaner equivalence ratios, and there is not much room for improvement. In general, optimum

NO_x conversion levels are observed for all temperatures tested, which is to be expected for this particular V₂O₅-based SCR catalyst at the tested temperature range.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

Figure 4. Effect of temperature on NO_x conversion for a) 0% H₂, b) 20% H₂, c) 40% H₂, d) 60% H₂, e) 80% H₂ and f) 100% H₂ ($\Phi = 0.98$, NO = 350 ppm).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5. Effect of temperature on NO_x conversion for a) 0% H₂, b) 20% H₂, c) 40% H₂, d) 60% H₂, e) 80% H₂ and f) 100% H₂ ($\Phi = 0.5$, NO = 350 ppm).

While the impacts of equivalence ratio and temperature on SCR performance have been well established in the literature, the results that have been reported previously were for much lower water contents. The results presented here show that similar trends are observed for the higher water levels, representing higher hydrogen content in the fuel.

3.3 Effect of H₂ Content on NO_x Conversion

In order to demonstrate the effect of hydrogen content in the fuel on SCR performance, Figure 6 presents NO_x conversion results for different hydrogen content values (0%-100%) at equivalence ratios of 0.98 and 0.5, temperatures of 350 °C, 375 °C and 400 °C, and NO concentration of 350 ppm. It is worth mentioning that the data in Figure 6 are reproduced from Figures 4 and 5 to illustrate the relationship between NO_x conversion and hydrogen content.

T = 350 °C

(a)

(b)

T = 375 °C

(c)

(d)

T = 400 °C

(e)

(f)

Figure 6. Effect of hydrogen content in the fuel on NO_x conversion for a) $\Phi = 0.98$ at 350 °C, b) $\Phi = 0.5$ at 350 °C, c) $\Phi = 0.98$ at 375 °C, d) $\Phi = 0.5$ at 375 °C, e) $\Phi = 0.98$ at 400 °C and f) $\Phi = 0.5$ at 400 °C (NO = 350 ppm).

As mentioned earlier, the water vapor content in the flue gas varies depending on both the hydrogen-to-methane ratio and the equivalence ratio. At an equivalence ratio of 0.5 (lean combustion), the water content ranges from 10% for pure methane (0% H₂) to 19% for pure hydrogen (100% H₂). As the combustion mixture becomes less lean, approaching a stoichiometric mixture, the water content increases. For an equivalence ratio of 0.98, the water concentration ranges from 19% for pure methane to 34% for pure hydrogen, which is the highest concentration that was tested in this study. This trend highlights the increasing water production with higher hydrogen content due to the higher hydrogen-to-carbon ratio in the fuel, which could influence the SCR performance.

At lean conditions ($\phi = 0.5$), the flue gas contains excess oxygen, which enhances NO_x conversion efficiency regardless of fuel composition. Higher NO_x conversion is consistently observed at the leaner equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.5$) across all hydrogen fuel contents compared to the near-stoichiometric condition ($\Phi = 0.98$). With higher hydrogen fraction, the water content increases from 10% at 0% hydrogen to 19% at 100% hydrogen. This water increase does not significantly affect the conversion, as the surplus oxygen plays the dominant role in driving the reaction forward, but slightly higher conversion is observed for 100% hydrogen than 0% hydrogen. In contrast, at near-stoichiometric conditions ($\phi = 0.98$), the role of water vapor becomes more prominent. As the hydrogen content increases from 0% to 60%, the water concentration in the flue gas rises from 19% to 23%, and NO_x conversion improves consistently across all the temperatures tested (350, 375, and 400 °C). However, further increasing the hydrogen content to 100% raises the water level to 34%, while the NO_x conversion drops back to a similar level observed for 0% hydrogen, but slightly higher. This indicates that the enhancement seen with moderate hydrogen addition (up to 60%) does not continue at higher hydrogen contents and a non-monotonic change in NO_x conversion is observed as the water content increases, potentially due to altered surface chemistry playing a role in the SCR mechanism. This trend suggests that moderate water levels

support improved NO_x conversion, hence the hydrogen-rich combustion conditions seem favorable for SCR activity.

Overall, the addition of hydrogen into the fuel, in other words, the increase of water content in the flue gas does not result in a decrease in NO_x conversion, it even increases conversion for up to 60% hydrogen. Therefore, the SCR units can be operated without any modifications when switching to blends of hydrogen and natural gas.

3.4 Effect of NO and SO₂ Concentrations on NO_x Conversion

In this section, the effect of increased NO concentration and the presence of SO₂ on SCR performance are investigated. As mentioned in the introduction, increasing the NO concentration can impact the NO_x conversion. Several studies have observed both increasing and decreasing NO_x emissions with hydrogen fuel addition into various stationary and residential power applications and the change could depend on the type of burner that is used. While the influence of hydrogen blending on NO_x emissions is not clear yet, increased NO_x levels are tested here to see if extremely high levels could still be mitigated in the SCR unit at high water content in the flue gas as a result of hydrogen addition. Figure 7 shows the results from SCR experiments performed with an increased NO concentration of 1000 ppm for different hydrogen content values (0%-100%) at equivalence ratios of 0.98 and 0.5 and a temperature of 350 °C.

Figure 7. Effect of NO concentration on NO_x conversion for a) $\Phi = 0.98$ and b) $\Phi = 0.5$ ($T = 350$ °C).

At a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio (Figure 7a), an increased NO concentration of 1000 ppm slightly decreases NO_x conversion in comparison to a NO concentration of 350 ppm, potentially due to the catalyst active sites becoming saturated at higher NO concentrations. Alternatively, at a leaner equivalence ratio (Figure 7b), the large amount of excess oxygen present in the flue gas increases SCR activity allowing NO_x conversion to remain unaffected at a NO concentration of 1000 ppm. In addition, hydrogen fuel addition at a higher NO concentration of 1000 ppm does not have an inhibitory effect on NO_x conversion across the 0%–100% hydrogen content range; however, a slight increase in conversion is observed up to 60% hydrogen for the near-stoichiometric case, consistent with the trend seen at lower NO concentrations.

Furthermore, the effect of the presence of SO₂ at various concentrations (30-500 ppm) on NO_x conversion is shown in Figure 8 for various hydrogen contents (0%-100%) and equivalence ratios of 0.98 and 0.5 at 350 °C. Notably, the upper end of this SO₂ range (500 ppm) represents a relatively high concentration, allowing for a more rigorous assessment of catalyst resistance to sulfur poisoning under severe conditions. As the SO₂ concentration increases from 30 ppm to 500 ppm, its impact on NO_x conversion becomes increasingly significant. At a low SO₂ concentration of 30 ppm, NO_x conversion remains largely unaffected for both near-stoichiometric ($\Phi = 0.98$) and lean ($\Phi = 0.5$) conditions, indicating that limited SO₂ adsorption does not substantially block the active sites required for the NH₃-SCR reaction. However, at 100 ppm SO₂, a clear distinction emerges between the two equivalence ratios: NO_x conversion remains stable at the near-stoichiometric ratio ($\Phi = 0.98$), while a slight decrease is observed under lean conditions ($\Phi = 0.5$). This difference is attributed to the presence of excess oxygen at $\Phi = 0.5$, which promotes the oxidation of SO₂ to SO₃, which could lead to the subsequent formation of stable sulfite or sulfate species that irreversibly occupy the catalyst's active sites, thereby inhibiting NO_x reduction. These findings are consistent with established literature, which highlights the critical role of oxygen in accelerating sulfate formation and catalyst deactivation under high SO₂ exposure [78, 79]. A previous study [58], which investigated the oxidation of SO₂ to SO₃ over supported vanadia catalysts has demonstrated that the conversion of SO₂ to SO₃ is dependent on the oxygen partial pressure in the reaction environment. Specifically, higher oxygen levels promote the oxidation of

SO₂ to SO₃, which can then lead to the formation of surface sulfite or sulfate species. Therefore, a more pronounced effect of SO₂ on NO_x conversion is expected for the lean conditions where excess oxygen is present compared to the stoichiometric case, similar to the trend observed in this study.

At higher SO₂ concentrations, both equivalence ratio cases are impacted. At a SO₂ concentration of 500 ppm, NO_x conversion is noticeably decreased for all the conditions, with a bigger decrease for $\Phi = 0.5$, reflecting widespread site saturation and severe sulfur poisoning. Interestingly, for both $\Phi = 0.98$ and $\Phi = 0.5$, NO_x conversion is higher for the 100% hydrogen cases compared to 0% hydrogen cases, implying that the presence of higher water vapor content in the flue gas improves the sulfur resistance of the catalyst. Previous studies have shown that surface sulfate species on the TiO₂ surface exposed to water vapor can enhance surface acidity and increase the number of active sites available for adsorption and activation of NH₃ and increase the SCR reaction rate for V₂O₅-TiO₂ catalysts [65, 80]. This effect could explain the improved resistance to SO₂ observed for the 100% hydrogen cases, due to the higher water content in the flue gas expected for these conditions. Further evaluation of this will be provided in the following section with the support of the characterization results.

Figure 8. Effect of SO₂ and H₂O on NO_x conversion for a) $\Phi = 0.98$ and b) $\Phi = 0.5$ ($T = 350$ °C, NO = 350 ppm).

3.5 Catalyst Characterization

To further probe the effect of hydrogen blending on NH₃-SCR in the presence of SO₂, a series of catalyst characterization experiments were conducted before and after the SCR experiments to analyze both the fresh and used catalysts. In addition, XPS was used to identify sulfur species on the surface of the catalyst samples exposed to 100 ppm SO₂ and the S 2p spectra for different equivalence ratios and hydrogen blends are provided in Figure 9. For 0% hydrogen with both near-stoichiometric ($\Phi=0.98$) and lean ($\Phi=0.5$) equivalence ratios (Figures 9a and 9c), the spectra show only the presence of a sulfite (SO₃²⁻) peak. However, for 100% hydrogen (Figures 9b and 9d), a sulfate (SO₄²⁻) peak becomes present in addition to the sulfite peak with the sulfate peak being more dominant for $\Phi=0.98$ (Figure 9b), and the sulfite peak becoming more apparent for $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9d). For 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9d), the water content in the flue gas (19%) is identical to that of 0% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$ (Figure 9a); however, there is a clear difference in the sulfur species present on the catalyst surface. The presence of the sulfate peak for 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9d) may be due to a higher amount of oxygen (9.5%) in the flue gas as opposed to very low oxygen (0.4%) for 0% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$ (Figure 9a). However, 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$ (Figure 9b) also has the same level of oxygen (0.3%), but the water content is significantly higher (34% vs. 19%), which is likely responsible for the sulfate formation. Similarly, 0% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9c) and 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9d) have the same amount of oxygen (10% vs. 9.5%), and a sulfate peak is present for the case of 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ because the water content is higher (19% vs. 10%). While both 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$ (Figure 9b) and 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.5$ (Figure 9d) have the presence of sulfate peaks, the sulfate peak for 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$ is much larger and more dominant compared to the sulfite peak. While there is a lack of excess oxygen in the flue gas for 100% hydrogen with $\Phi=0.98$, there is a large amount of water content, indicating that the strong presence of sulfate is largely dependent on the amount of water content present in the flue gas. In summary, comparison of all four spectra reveals two conclusions: i) for the same oxygen content in the flue gas, higher water content results in sulfate formation, and ii) for the same water content in the flue gas, sulfate formation is observed for the case with higher oxygen in the flue

gas, indicating that both water and oxygen level play a role on the sulfur chemistry on the catalyst surface.

Figure 9. S 2p core level spectra of the catalysts exposed to flue gas of a) 0% H₂ with $\Phi=0.98$, b) 100% H₂ with $\Phi=0.98$, c) 0% H₂ with $\Phi=0.5$, d) 100% H₂ with $\Phi=0.5$ ($T = 350$ °C, NO = 350 ppm, SO₂ = 100ppm).

To further elucidate SO₂ oxidation to SO₃ during the SCR reaction, the salt method was used to detect the presence of SO₃ in the gas phase. Figure 10a shows the measured SO₃ concentration in the outlet of the reactor as a function of the SO₂ concentration in the reactor inlet for different hydrogen contents in the fuel (0% and 100%) and equivalence ratios of 0.98 and 0.5

at 350 °C. In order to show the influence of water content, measured SO₃ values for the different conditions tested are also plotted as a function of the water concentration corresponding to each case (Figure 10b). For a better comparison, Table 1 is presented with the water and oxygen concentrations for each case as well as the measured SO₃ concentration and NO_x conversion to show their relation.

Figure 10. Gas phase SO₃ concentration in the reactor outlet as function of a) SO₂ concentration in the reactor inlet and b) H₂O concentration in the reactor inlet (T = 350 °C, NO = 350 ppm).

Table 1. Gas phase SO₃ concentration and NO_x conversion for different hydrogen contents in the fuel and equivalence ratios at 350 °C. Inlet water, oxygen and SO₂ concentrations for each case are also provided.

Test Condition	Inlet H ₂ O (%)	Inlet O ₂ (%)	Inlet SO ₂ (ppm)	Outlet SO ₃ (ppm)	NO _x conversion (%)
$\Phi=0.98, 0\% \text{ H}_2$	19	0.4	100	69	83
$\Phi=0.98, 100\% \text{ H}_2$	34	0.3	100	36	86
$\Phi=0.5, 0\% \text{ H}_2$	10	10	100	64	83
$\Phi=0.5, 100\% \text{ H}_2$	19	9.5	100	54	86
$\Phi=0.98, 0\% \text{ H}_2$	19	0.4	500	185	68
$\Phi=0.98, 100\% \text{ H}_2$	34	0.3	500	100	75
$\Phi=0.5, 0\% \text{ H}_2$	10	10	500	250	58
$\Phi=0.5, 100\% \text{ H}_2$	19	9.5	500	180	67

Firstly, the detection of SO_3 in the reactor outlet confirms the oxidation of SO_2 to SO_3 by the SCR catalyst. More SO_3 is observed as the amount of SO_2 is increased from 100 ppm to 500 ppm. Secondly, lean cases, where the oxygen concentration is higher, result in more SO_2 oxidation. Higher concentration of SO_3 was observed for the 0% hydrogen cases and the SO_3 concentration is less for the 100 % hydrogen cases for both equivalence ratios. This is clearly a result of the higher water content with the higher hydrogen percentage in the fuel as evident from Figure 10b where the SO_3 concentration decreases almost linearly with increased water content in the flue gas, representing higher hydrogen content in the fuel. These results emphasize the complex interplay between water, oxygen, and sulfur oxidation pathways.

Figure 11. NO_x conversion vs. gas phase SO_3 concentration in the reactor outlet.

In addition, Figure 11 shows the impact of SO_3 concentration on NO_x conversion. There is an almost linear trend, where increasing SO_3 leads to a reduction in NO_x conversion, suggesting catalyst deactivation. This effect is more significant at the higher SO_2 inlet concentration of 500 ppm, indicating that elevated sulfur levels enhance the inhibitory impact of SO_3 on SCR performance. This inhibitory effect can be explained by analyzing both the gas-phase SO_3 and the sulfur speciation observed on the catalyst surface using XPS. As observed from the XPS results, sulfate species form on the surface in the 100% hydrogen cases due to the increased water content in the flue gas. For those cases, the amount of SO_3 in the gas phase is lower compared to the 0% hydrogen cases where the water content is lower. For the cases where the SO_3 content is lower,

the NO_x conversion is higher. Therefore, the presence of higher water in the flue gas (100% hydrogen) helps form sulfate compounds on the catalyst, which is linked to increased acidity and improved resistance to sulfur deactivation [64, 65, 80, 81], and less SO_3 is released in the gas phase, which results in an increase in NO_x conversion. On the other hand, the NO_x conversion decreases in cases where only sulfite species are formed on the catalyst and more SO_3 is released into the gas phase, which occurs at lower water levels in the flue gas (0% hydrogen). In other words, the higher water content in the flue gas resulting from hydrogen blending makes the catalyst more resistant to sulfur poisoning. Figure 12 summarizes these findings and shows how hydrogen blending would impact SO_2 oxidation and NO_x reduction over the SCR catalyst. In the figure, less SO_3 in the gas phase and higher NO_x conversion are depicted for the 100% hydrogen case where sulfate formation is observed in addition to sulfite species on the catalyst surface while more SO_3 in the gas phase is observed along with sulfite formation on the catalyst for the 0% hydrogen case, resulting in lower NO_x conversion.

Figure 12. Proposed mechanism for SO_2 oxidation and NO_x reduction over SCR catalysts for 0% H_2 and 100% H_2 .

4. Conclusions

This study evaluated the effect of blending hydrogen into methane on the performance of a commercial $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ SCR catalyst and demonstrated that blending up to 100% hydrogen does not inhibit NO_x conversion in the SCR process, even at high water vapor concentrations (as high as 34%) resulting from hydrogen combustion. The impact of hydrogen blending on NO_x

conversion depends on the level of hydrogen content in the fuel, in other words, the water content in the flue gas. For the near-stoichiometric condition ($\Phi = 0.98$), as the hydrogen content increases from 0% to 60%, NO_x conversion improves consistently across all the temperatures that were tested (350, 375, and 400 °C) while increasing the hydrogen content further lowers the NO_x conversion back to a similar level observed for 0% hydrogen, but slightly higher. This non-monotonic trend suggests that moderate water levels support improved NO_x conversion, while excessive water content may neutralize these benefits, potentially due to the surface species being altered in the presence of water. For the lean condition ($\Phi = 0.98$), the increase in hydrogen content does not significantly affect NO_x conversion, as the excess oxygen plays the dominant role in driving the reaction forward, but slightly higher conversion is observed for 100% hydrogen than 0% hydrogen, similar to the near-stoichiometric case.

Additionally, the effects of various parameters such as the equivalence ratio, temperature, NO concentration and the presence of SO_2 on NO_x conversion were investigated in an SCR environment with high water content, representing the flue gas environment of hydrogen/methane blends. The findings reveal that NO_x conversion at a lean equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.5$) is greater than that of a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio ($\Phi = 0.98$) due to the abundance of excess oxygen, which enhances both the standard and fast SCR reaction pathways and regenerates active sites. A similar trend is also observed at higher NO concentrations with a lean equivalence ratio displaying no change in NO_x conversion, as opposed to a near-stoichiometric equivalence ratio, which experienced a slight decrease in SCR activity when increasing the NO concentration from 300ppm to 1000ppm. Increasing the temperature from 350 °C to 400 °C results in a modest improvement in NO_x conversion under near-stoichiometric conditions, while the conversion for the lean case does not change much since it is already high due to the presence of the excess oxygen. While the impacts of equivalence ratio and temperature on SCR performance are well established in the literature for much lower water contents, the results presented here demonstrate that similar trends are observed for the higher water levels (up to 34%), representing higher hydrogen content in the fuel.

Moreover, SO_2 exposure reduces the SCR performance, and the impact gets worse as the SO_2 concentration increases. However, for both equivalence ratios, NO_x conversion is improved

when using 100% hydrogen compared to the case of no hydrogen addition, implying that the presence of higher water vapor content in the flue gas improves the sulfur resistance of the catalyst. Post-reaction catalyst characterization reveals that high water content associated with high-hydrogen-content in the fuel promotes the formation of sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) on the catalyst surface rather than sulfite (SO_3^{2-}), which is linked to increased surface acidity and improved resistance to sulfur deactivation in the presence of water. Further analysis of SO_3 in the gas phase confirms that higher water content results in less SO_3 in the gas phase, supporting the role of water vapor in redirecting sulfur pathways toward surface-bound sulfates rather than volatile SO_3 . This shift enhances NO_x conversion making the catalyst more resistant to sulfur.

While further investigation of the underlying mechanisms involving hydrogen blending and the role of water on SCR activity is necessary, this study shows how the higher water content as a result of hydrogen blending affects the performance of the SCR catalyst, which has not been tested before. When considering the end goal of hydrogen fuel implementation into stationary power applications, the results of this study offer promising outlooks. The findings suggest that SCR systems can continue to operate effectively without modification when transitioning to hydrogen–natural gas fuel blends.

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Effect of Hydrogen Addition in Natural Gas on Selective Catalytic Reduction of NO_x in Power Plants – Phase II

1. Introduction

Combustion of H₂/NG blends significantly alters the flue gas composition, by elevating the water vapor (H₂O) concentration, which could potentially introduce challenges for the control of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions. In Phase I of this study, the authors systematically investigated hydrogen blending up to 100%, providing novel insights into SCR performance of a commercial vanadia-based catalyst (V₂O₅–WO₃/TiO₂). This study demonstrated that blending hydrogen into methane up to 100% does not inhibit NO_x conversion in the SCR process, even at high water vapor concentrations resulting from hydrogen combustion. Furthermore, although sulfur dioxide (SO₂) exposure reduces SCR performance, using pure hydrogen as the fuel improves sulfur resistance of the catalyst by increasing water vapor concentration in the flue gas, which promotes the formation of surface-bound sulfates (SO₄²⁻) over sulfites (SO₃²⁻) and decreases gaseous sulfur trioxide (SO₃) formation. Overall, these findings demonstrate that SCR systems can effectively operate without modification when transitioning to hydrogen–natural gas fuel blends, offering a viable pathway to decarbonize stationary power systems while maintaining robust NO_x control performance. However, while these findings underscore the operational feasibility of SCR in hydrogen–natural gas fuel systems, the mechanistic understanding of surface species evolution under varying flue gas environments remains limited. Therefore, a detailed in-situ diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier transform spectroscopy (DRIFTS) investigation is necessary to elucidate the molecular-level interactions of adsorbed NH₃, NO, and H₂O species on the catalyst surface, especially in the presence of SO₂. Such insights are critical to confirm the proposed reaction pathways, identify the nature of active and deactivating species, and ultimately guide catalyst optimization for hydrogen-integrated stationary power applications.

Previously, several studies have been performed to investigate the SCR mechanism of vanadia/titania (V₂O₅/TiO₂) catalysts, specifically including the effects of water vapor and SO₂. Even though these studies were performed with low water concentrations and do not represent the flue gas environment of H₂/NG blends, an overview of their observations is still provided here to provide insights into the catalyst behavior in the presence of water and SO₂. It has been shown that water vapor alters the active sites on the catalyst surface and changes the distribution of Lewis and

Brønsted acid sites [1]. Water vapor is known to inhibit the activity of common SCR catalysts, particularly at low temperatures ($<277^{\circ}\text{C}$). However, the incorporation of tungsten oxide (WO_3) significantly enhances the catalyst's SCR activity both in dry and wet conditions [2]. In the typical SCR temperature window of $300\text{--}400^{\circ}\text{C}$, studies have shown that water vapor at around $\sim 1\%$ can cause a measurable decrease in SCR activity; however, further increases in water concentration higher than 5% have negligible additional impact, indicating a saturation effect in inhibition [3, 4]. Importantly, above a certain threshold, the catalyst surface becomes saturated with adsorbed water, and additional water does not further decrease the reaction rate, resulting in the observed plateau. Another study employing in-situ IR spectroscopy has observed a slight decline in catalytic activity of supported $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts at 390°C in the presence of 1.7% water vapor accompanied by an increase in surface ammonium (NH_4^+) species on Brønsted acid sites [5]. This increase likely results from the conversion of Lewis acid sites into Brønsted acid sites under moist conditions [6, 7]. Overall, the inhibitory effect of water is thought to result from two primary mechanisms [1]: (1) competitive adsorption with NO and NH_3 , and/or (2) suppression of the reaction between NO and adsorbed NH_3 [3, 8-10]; however, further studies about the role of water in SCR activity are needed [1].

Regarding the impact of sulfur species in the flue gas, SCR catalysts are known to oxidize SO_2 to SO_3 , which forms acid rain, corrodes equipment, and generates ammonium salts that deactivate catalysts and reduce efficiency [11]. SCR catalysts should maximize NO_x reduction while keeping SO_3 formation below $1\text{--}2\%$ to prevent corrosion and catalyst fouling [1, 12]. The adsorption behavior of SO_2 and SO_3 on TiO_2 and supported $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ has been extensively studied. Without O_2 , SO_2 adsorbs as either physisorbed SO_2 or chemisorbed sulfite (SO_3), depending on the temperature [13]. In the presence of O_2 and at temperatures above 200°C , sulfites convert into more stable sulfate (SO_4) species that bond strongly to the TiO_2 support [11]. These surface sulfates increase Brønsted acidity upon exposure to moisture by forming acidic S-OH groups [14]. On $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts, SO_4 species preferentially bind to TiO_2 rather than vanadia due to repulsive interactions. A systematic study of SCR of NO by NH_3 over $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ at 350°C showed that catalyst activity peaks at about half a monolayer of vanadia, then declines due to loss of TiO_2 -associated acid sites [15]. Moreover, SO_2 promotes activity only at low vanadia coverage through sulfate formation on the TiO_2 surface [15]. In addition, tungsten oxide promotion in $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts significantly enhances SCR activity by increasing Brønsted acidity. Unlike vanadia,

tungsten oxide shows much lower turnover frequency for SO₂ oxidation, reducing undesired SO₃ formation. Thus, WO₃ acts as an effective additive, improving NO reduction efficiency while minimizing SO₂ oxidation and ammonium sulfate deposition at low temperatures [16]. Furthermore, DFT studies show that SO₂ is oxidized to SO₃ and, with NH₃ and H₂O, forms NH₄HSO₄, the main cause of SO₂ poisoning. On MoO₃/V₂O₅ surfaces, electron transfer enables NH₄⁺ to react on V₂O₅ while HSO₄⁻ decomposes on MoO₃ into SO₃ and H₂O, allowing continuous NH₄HSO₄ removal. The negatively charged V₂O₅ surface also creates Brønsted acid sites, lowering the NH₃ dissociation barrier and enhancing SCR activity [17].

Despite these previous studies, the mechanistic role of water and SO₂ interactions in SCR processes, particularly at the surface molecular level, remains insufficiently understood, especially for high water vapor environments representing the flue gas of H₂/NG blends. Motivated by these challenges, this study employs in-situ DRIFTS to investigate surface species evolution on V₂O₅–WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts exposed to various flue gas mixtures of H₂/NG blends including SO₂ and individual flue gas components. By systematically analyzing catalyst behavior under relevant conditions, this work aims to elucidate how the flue gas of hydrogen-enriched fuels influences NH₃ and NO adsorption, surface acidity, and sulfur tolerance. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this work is the first to investigate SCR catalyst behavior under such elevated water vapor concentrations, which is characteristic of hydrogen-enriched combustion. The insights gained provide a basis for optimizing SCR catalyst design and operation to ensure robust NO_x control in emerging hydrogen-rich fuel scenarios.

2. Methodology

2.1. DRIFT Spectroscopy Technique

DRIFT spectroscopy was employed to study the evolution of surface species on a commercial V₂O₅–WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst during the SCR reaction. DRIFTS is a powerful analytical technique used in catalysis and materials science to study surface interactions under real reaction conditions, often referred to as "operando" measurements. Unlike traditional infrared spectroscopy, DRIFTS can be used on powdered samples and does not require complex sample preparation. DRIFTS is particularly sensitive to species adsorbed on the surface of solid catalysts. This is crucial because catalytic reactions often occur on the surface, and detecting these species provides insight into what is really happening during the reaction. The technique allows for continuous monitoring of

the surface as gases pass over the catalyst. This means one can observe changes in surface species and intermediates as the reaction proceeds, not just before and after. By detecting the infrared absorption of vibrational modes of molecules, DRIFTS helps identify functional groups, such as NH, NO, OH, or CO, that are adsorbed on the catalyst surface. It provides valuable information about where and how molecules bind to the catalyst, what intermediates form during the reaction, and what changes occur in response to variables like temperature, gas composition, or catalyst treatment. By identifying these species and tracking their evolution, DRIFTS helps researchers propose or validate reaction mechanisms. For example, one could see the formation of nitrate or ammonium species during the SCR process and how they are affected by high water content that arises from hydrogen blending.

2.2 Experimental Conditions

The SCR environment consists of the flue gas components, CO₂, H₂O, O₂, SO₂, and the SCR reaction components NO and NH₃. The catalyst samples were exposed to the SCR reactants, NO and NH₃, individually, and in the presence of the other flue gas components to see their effects on the adsorption of NO and NH₃ and the SCR reaction. Exposing the catalyst to the reactants separately sheds light into how H₂O and O₂ influence the adsorption of each reactant on the catalyst surface. Therefore, NH₃ adsorption was tested individually, as well as in combination with 10% O₂, 10% H₂O, 20% H₂O, and 34% H₂O. Additional mixtures included NH₃ with both 10% O₂ and 10% H₂O, and with 10% O₂ and 20% H₂O. Similarly, NO was tested individually and in the presence of 10% O₂, 10% H₂O, 20% H₂O, 34% H₂O, and in combinations containing both 10% O₂ and 10% or 20% H₂O. Additionally, NH₃ and NO were introduced simultaneously along with 10% O₂, 10% H₂O, 20% H₂O, 34% H₂O, and with both 10% O₂ and 10% or 20% H₂O, creating the SCR environment. The test matrix, shown in Table 1, lists the various gas compositions that were tested to evaluate surface species under varying conditions. For all of these tests, 800 ppm of NO and NH₃ was used in addition to the flue gas components with balance N₂.

Table 1. Test matrix of the experiments.

NH ₃ Adsorption	NO Adsorption	NH ₃ + NO Adsorption
NH ₃ + N ₂	NO + N ₂	NH ₃ + NO + N ₂
NH ₃ + 10% O ₂ + N ₂	NO + 10% O ₂ + N ₂	NH ₃ + NO + 10% O ₂ + N ₂
NH ₃ + 10% H ₂ O + N ₂	NO + 10% H ₂ O + N ₂	NH ₃ + NO + 10% H ₂ O + N ₂

The varying H₂O content in these mixtures serve to simulate different H₂ concentrations in the fuel mixture, with dry conditions (0% H₂O) acting as a baseline. Different O₂ concentrations represent different equivalence ratios (Φ) for the fuel-air mixture. Table 2 shows the H₂O and O₂ concentrations in the flue gas of pure methane and pure hydrogen with different equivalence ratios, representing flue gases of different stationary power applications. For example, an equivalence ratio of 0.5 would represent fuel-lean conditions of a gas turbine with excess oxygen presence, while an equivalence ratio of 0.98 represents near-stoichiometric conditions of a boiler.

Table 2. Water and oxygen concentrations in the flue gas for different fuel-air mixtures.

Fuel-oxidizer mixture	H ₂ O (%)	O ₂ (%)
$\Phi = 0.98, 100\% \text{CH}_4$	19	0.4
$\Phi = 0.98, 100\% \text{H}_2$	34	0.3
$\Phi = 0.5, 100\% \text{CH}_4$	10	10
$\Phi = 0.5, 100\% \text{H}_2$	19	9.5

Each composition listed in Table 1 was tested on both fresh and used catalysts that were exposed to SO₂. The used catalysts were prepared by exposing fresh catalyst samples to the SCR environment including 500 ppm SO₂ for 4 hours, at equivalence ratios of 0.5 and 0.98, mimicking post-combustion flue gases of different CH₄/H₂ blends. Since the DRIFTS cell cannot accommodate SO₂ exposure due to material limitations, this pre-treatment was performed separately in an SCR reactor. Details of the packed-bed reactor set-up used for these experiments, and the NO_x conversion results can be found in the Phase I section of the report. These reaction conditions are similar to those later applied in the DRIFTS cell, ensuring consistency in surface species formation. To represent the conditions of the SCR experiments listed in Table 2, H₂O levels of 10, 20 and 34%, and O₂ levels of 0 and 10% were selected for the DRIFTS experiments. After the SCR reaction in the packed-bed reactor, the used catalysts were transferred to the DRIFTS cell for in-situ surface analysis to investigate if the adsorption of NO, NH₃ and a mixture of NO and NH₃, or the reaction of NO and NH₃ on the surface would be impacted when the catalyst

was previously exposed to SO₂. Overall, this matrix enables a detailed assessment of how oxygen, water vapor, and sulfur exposure influence the adsorption behavior of NH₃, NO, and their combination under operando conditions to investigate the impact of hydrogen blending on the SCR catalyst.

2.3 Experimental Set-up

Figure 1 illustrates the experimental set-up that was employed to study catalyst behavior. The set-up consists of a high-temperature DRIFTS cell by Harrick, fitted with ZnSe windows, that is mounted on a Bruker Tensor II FTIR spectrometer that is equipped with an MCT detector cooled by liquid nitrogen. For each test, approximately 600 μg of a commercial SCR catalyst (V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂) was added and leveled without any additional compression. The cell was then preheated under a nitrogen flow to remove surface contaminants and moisture. The experiments were conducted at 250°C; however, the fresh catalysts were pretreated at a higher temperature before the tests. Before the used catalysts were tested in the SCR reactor, they were treated at 550 °C for 1 hour. Since the fresh catalysts did not go through this process, they were preheated at 450 °C for over 2 hours to remove any excess moisture, then the temperature was reduced to 250°C.

Figure 1. Experimental set-up.

For the experiments involving water vapor exposure, the catalyst was initially treated with water vapor to establish a stable background before introducing any reactive gases. Water vapor was generated using the evaporator system depicted in Figure 1. In this setup, liquid water was delivered via a HPLC pump (Shimadzu LC-10AD VP), with the flow rate carefully adjusted to match the desired vapor concentration. To ensure complete vaporization, the evaporator column was packed with silica glass beads, increasing residence time and promoting full evaporation of water entering the column. The column was wrapped with a heat tape and maintained at the target

temperature using a VariAC-controlled heating system. Initial background spectra were recorded once the temperature and gas flow were stabilized. Absorbance spectra in the range of 6000-1200 cm^{-1} (64 scans) were collected every 2 minutes until the spectra no longer showed any changes, indicating water saturation. A duration of 2 hours was allotted to ensure complete saturation of the catalyst surface with water vapor. This preconditioning step allowed for the stabilization of background spectra, ensuring that any subsequent spectral changes observed during the experiment could be attributed solely to the adsorption of the SCR gas mixture on the catalyst surface rather than residual water adsorption dynamics. After this step, a small slipstream of 20 ml/min of the gas mixture at total flow rate of 600 ml/min was directed to the DRIFTS cell for experimentation in order not to cause disruption to the sample from a high flow rate. Absorption spectra were continuously collected for a total duration of 2 hours following the introduction of the SCR gas mixture. The spectra recorded at 120 min were selected for discussion in this report, as it represents the steady-state surface species distribution after prolonged exposure and the time-resolved spectra are provided in the Appendix Section.

3. Results and Discussion

The following sections analyze the surface interactions observed in the DRIFTS experiments for both fresh and used catalysts under various gas compositions. By systematically evaluating the individual and combined adsorption of NH_3 and NO , along with the effects of water vapor and oxygen, the results offer insights into the nature of active sites, competitive adsorption behavior, and the impact of sulfur poisoning on SCR performance.

3.1 Experiments with NH_3

This section investigates how NH_3 adsorbs onto the catalyst surface under varying conditions, including its individual adsorption, and interactions in the presence of O_2 and/or water vapor at different levels (10%, 20%, and 34%). These experiments aim to reveal how water and O_2 impact NH_3 adsorption and surface interactions. The insights gained enhance the understanding of NH_3 activation mechanisms and adsorption dynamics critical to SCR reaction efficiency.

Figure 2 illustrates the in-situ DRIFT spectra for NH_3 adsorption on $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts, comparing fresh (A-C) and used (D-F) surfaces across different gas environments. The full-range spectra (A, D) capture the overall vibrational profile, while zoomed-in views highlight detailed

interactions at high (B, E) and low (C, F) wavenumbers. The results indicate that both Lewis and Brønsted acid sites actively participate in NH₃ adsorption on the V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ surface [18, 19]. Both on the fresh (A-C) and used catalysts (D-F), NH₃ adsorption results in the appearance of eight distinct peaks corresponding to interactions with Brønsted and Lewis acid sites as shown in spectrum (a) in Figure 2 (A and D for the fresh catalyst and used catalyst, respectively). When bonded on Brønsted acid sites, NH₃ is protonated to form NH₄⁺, which exhibits specific vibrational modes: asymmetric NH₄⁺ bending vibrations appear in the range of 1400-1450 cm⁻¹ [20, 21], symmetric NH₄⁺ bending vibrations are observed at 1670-1700 cm⁻¹ [22, 23], and NH₄⁺ symmetric stretching vibrations occur at approximately 3261 cm⁻¹ [23-25]. On the other hand, NH₃ coordinated to Lewis acid sites display a different set of vibrational characteristics. N-H stretching vibrations are broad, spanning 3300-3400 cm⁻¹ [26, 27] and 3100-3200 cm⁻¹ [28], due to hydrogen bonding effects. Additionally, coordinated NH₃ bending vibrations are detected at approximately 1600-1620 cm⁻¹ [23, 27, 29]. V-NH₃ coordination leads to symmetric deformation modes around 1250 and 1339 cm⁻¹ [27]. These vibrational features collectively provide insight into the nature of NH₃ adsorption and its interactions with the surface acid sites. Besides the eight positive peaks explained above as characteristic features of NH₃ adsorption, one negative peak was identified. The negative band observed around approximately 3650 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum during NH₃ adsorption on vanadyl surfaces is a clear indication of surface hydroxyl group consumption [30, 31]. This peak represents the disappearance of surface OH groups upon adsorption of NH₃. The interaction between NH₃ and Brønsted acid sites on the catalyst surface is highlighted by this observation, as NH₃ accepts a proton from the hydroxyl groups, forming NH₄⁺ species. This interaction is captured in the reaction: $V-OH + NH_3 \rightarrow V-O^- + NH_4^+$, which underscores the role of Brønsted acid sites in facilitating NH₃ adsorption and the subsequent formation of NH₄⁺ [4, 32]. The negative peak thus provides critical insights into the surface chemistry and adsorption mechanism on a vanadia-based catalyst.

Figure 2: In-situ DRIFT spectra of NH₃ on fresh (A-C) and used (D-F) V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under varying gas compositions. Panels A and D: full-range spectra (4000-1200 cm⁻¹); B and E: high-wavenumber region (3700-3100 cm⁻¹); C and F: low-wavenumber region (1800-1200 cm⁻¹).

Figure 3 presents the quantitative DRIFTS analysis of NH₃ adsorption on fresh (Panels A and B) and used (Panels C and D) V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under various gas compositions. In order to evaluate the distribution of different surface species under different environments, areas under the

peaks for each spectrum shown in Figure 2 were integrated to be able to quantitatively compare how the distribution of peaks associated with different surface species is changing as a result of the presence of O₂ and/or H₂O. In Panels A and C, integrated peak areas were calculated for the characteristic vibrational bands associated with both coordinated NH₃ species (e.g., 3377, 3154, 1600, 1339, and 1250 cm⁻¹) and protonated NH₄⁺ species (e.g., 3261, 1684, and 1427 cm⁻¹) and each peak area was divided by the total area of all peaks, representing the percentage of each surface species among others. Panels B and D summarize the combined contributions of these peak areas into two categories: coordinated ammonia on Lewis acid sites, denoted by L-NH₃, and protonated ammonia on Brønsted acid sites, denoted by B-NH₄⁺, expressed as percentages of the total ammonia-related signal. This analysis enables comparison of different NH₃ adsorption modes and speciation between fresh and used catalyst surfaces under different conditions.

Figure 3: Quantitative analysis of integrated DRIFTS peak areas for NH₃ and related species adsorbed on fresh (A and B) and used (C and D) V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under varying gas compositions and humidity levels at 250 °C. Panels A and C display integrations from the high and low wavenumber regions. Panels B and D summarize the total integrated intensities of coordinated (L-NH₃) versus protonated ammonia (B-NH₄⁺).

For the NH₃-only condition (spectra (a) in Figure 2), without O₂ and H₂O in the stream, adsorption occurs exclusively via NH₃, enabling the identification of NH₃ adsorption modes. On the fresh catalyst (Panels A and B in Figure 3), adsorbed NH₃ species show a balanced distribution of coordinated ammonia (L-NH₃) at 35.69% and protonated ammonia (B-NH₄⁺) at 64.31%, indicating active Lewis and Brønsted acid sites. For the used catalyst (Panels C and D in Figure 3), coordinated NH₃ decreases to 30.70% while NH₄⁺ increases to 69.30%, suggesting a shift toward Brønsted acidity after aging under the SCR environment with SO₂ exposure. While the

total amounts of coordinated vs. protonated ammonia are not too different for the fresh and used catalysts, the distribution of the peaks differs significantly. For the fresh catalyst, the Brønsted-associated protonated ammonia band at 1427 cm^{-1} is the largest contributor to the adsorbed NH_3 species on the surface; however, for the used catalyst, the intensity of the peak at 1427 cm^{-1} goes down accompanied by an increase in the intensities of the peaks at 3261 and 1684 cm^{-1} , which are also associated with protonated ammonia.

For the fresh catalyst, addition of 10% O_2 has a minimal impact on NH_3 adsorption behavior, as the total NH_4^+ content remains nearly constant, suggesting that the adsorption mechanism is largely unaffected. In contrast, the used catalyst exhibits a notable shift in adsorption characteristics upon O_2 introduction. For NH_3 with 10% O_2 , the total coordinated ammonia signal increases to 36.54%, mainly due to notable gains at 3377 cm^{-1} and 3154 cm^{-1} , indicating enhanced Lewis site utilization, bringing it back to a similar level of coordinated ammonia observed for the adsorption of NH_3 on the fresh catalyst. The total protonated ammonia signal decreases to 63.46%, with increases at 3261 cm^{-1} and 1339 cm^{-1} offset by a substantial decrease at 1427 cm^{-1} , similar to the change observed for NH_3 -only adsorption on the used catalyst. The observed enhancement in coordinated NH_3 adsorption on the surface of the used catalyst after O_2 introduction can be attributed to O_2 -induced site reactivation. For the used catalyst, prior exposure to the SCR environment with SO_2 likely resulted in partial blockage or reduction of Lewis acid sites through the formation of sulfur species on the surface [33] and the accumulation of reduced vanadia species (V^{4+}) as a result of the SCR reaction [34]. Introducing O_2 can reoxidize V^{4+} back to V^{5+} , restoring the electron-deficient Lewis centers that favor NH_3 coordination. Vanadia species undergo a redox cycle between $\text{V}^{5+}=\text{O}$ and $\text{V}^{4+}-\text{OH}$ during NO_x reduction, with the re-oxidation of V^{4+} back to V^{5+} identified as the rate-determining step [35]. In addition, O_2 may promote oxidative desorption of NH_4^+ species from weaker Brønsted sites, freeing surface area for NH_3 to coordinate on regenerated Lewis sites [36]. Because Brønsted sites on $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ are not uniform in strength, ranging from surface hydroxyls ($\text{V}-\text{OH}$) to $\text{W}-\text{OH}$ and $\text{Ti}-\text{OH}$ groups, O_2 interacts selectively, removing NH_4^+ from weaker sites while leaving stronger ones occupied. This non-uniform site reactivity explains the simultaneous increase and decrease in different Brønsted-associated bands. In contrast, the fresh catalyst already has fully accessible and unpoisoned Lewis sites, so O_2 introduction does not produce a significant net change in coordinated NH_3 adsorption, as there is little to regenerate or unblock. When comparing the time-resolved spectra for NH_3 on

the fresh (provided in Appendix, Figure 1S) and used catalysts (Figure 22S), the NH_3 peaks start developing after 30 minutes on the used catalyst, while they develop within the first 5 minutes on the fresh catalyst, due to sites not being available on the used catalyst in the beginning. However, when O_2 is added, the NH_3 peaks start developing right away on the used catalyst, confirming the hypothesis of O_2 replenishing the sites for NH_3 to adsorb. Overall, these results suggest that under lean conditions where O_2 is in excess, the oxidative environment can facilitate the restoration of acid sites for NH_3 to adsorb.

The addition of water vapor significantly influences NH_3 speciation on both the fresh and used catalysts, with the effects depending on the water concentration. As explained in the methodology, water was introduced at different levels (10, 20 and 34%) representing different flue gas environments. On the fresh catalyst, comparison of NH_3 only and $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panels A and B in Figure 3) reveals an increase in coordinated NH_3 from 35.69% to 41.94%, driven primarily by gains at 3377 and 1250 cm^{-1} , alongside a decrease in protonated ammonia, largely due to a reduction at 1427 cm^{-1} and a redistribution toward 1684 cm^{-1} , where NH_4^+ -related intensity increases. At 20% H_2O , representing the flue gas environment for 100% CH_4 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, comparing NH_3 only and $\text{NH}_3 + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ on the fresh catalyst (Panels A and B in Figure 3), coordinated NH_3 slightly decreases while NH_4^+ slightly increases. However, at 34% H_2O , representing the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, comparing NH_3 only and $\text{NH}_3 + 34\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panels A and B in Figure 3), total coordinated NH_3 slightly increases, with the main gain at 1250 cm^{-1} offset by a decrease at 1339 cm^{-1} . In parallel, total protonated ammonia shows a slight decrease primarily from the band at 1427 cm^{-1} , partially compensated by an increase at 1684 cm^{-1} . When comparing the results obtained with different levels of water, the following observations can be made. When increasing the water content from 10% H_2O to 20% H_2O , protonated ammonia increases. In contrast, going from 20% H_2O to 34% H_2O decreases protonated ammonia, suggesting that a non-monotonic behavior is observed with respect to the water concentration. In the previous SCR experiments reported in Phase I, NO_x conversion was also found to change with the water content in a non-monotonic behavior when SO_2 is not present. For the near-stoichiometric cases where excess oxygen is minimal ($\Phi = 0.98$ with 0.3-0.4% O_2), as the hydrogen content increases, going from 100% CH_4 (with 19% H_2O in the flue gas) to 100% H_2 (with 34% H_2O in the flue gas), the NO_x conversion first increased, then decreased back to a similar level observed for 100% CH_4 , but

slightly higher. The non-monotonic change in the surface speciation observed here where the amount of ammonia adsorbed on Brønsted sites first increases, then decreases when increasing the H₂O content from 10% to 34%, corresponds to the non-monotonic change in NO_x conversion observed in the previous SCR experiments.

Furthermore, when comparing the time-resolved spectra of NH₃ (provided in Appendix, Figure 1S) with NH₃ spectra in the presence of 10, 20 and 34% H₂O (Figures 3S-5S) on the fresh catalyst, it is observed that the NH₃ peaks start developing with a delay when the catalyst surface was exposed to water prior to NH₃ adsorption, with the delay getting longer as the H₂O concentration increases. This is likely due to H₂O taking up the sites and competing with NH₃. As time goes on NH₃ displaces the H₂O molecules and start adsorbing on the surface. It has been reported that the desorption of water in the absence of O₂ can lead to the formation of under-coordinated V⁴⁺ sites, which can act as new Lewis acid sites that NH₃ can bind to [37]. Consistently, there is an increase in Lewis sites observed in this study in the presence of 10% and 34% H₂O, but not with 20% H₂O.

For the used catalyst, comparison of NH₃ only and NH₃ + 10% H₂O (Panels C and D in Figure 3) shows a reduction in coordinated NH₃ (from 30.70% to 26.24%), mostly at 1600 cm⁻¹ and 3377 cm⁻¹, and an increase in protonated ammonia, mostly at 1427 cm⁻¹ with a decrease at 1684 cm⁻¹ and 3261 cm⁻¹, redistributing NH₄⁺ towards 1427 cm⁻¹. Comparing NH₃ only and NH₃ + 20% H₂O (Panels C and D in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O₂ content is negligible, a drastic drop in coordinated NH₃ (to 13.25%) and a sharp rise in protonated ammonia (to 86.75%) occur. As the water content increases from 10% to 20%, the increase in the protonated ammonia gets larger compared to NH₃ only. However, when comparing NH₃ only and NH₃ + 34% H₂O (Panels C and D in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O₂ content is negligible, the trend reverses: coordinated NH₃ increases (to 36.15%) and NH₄⁺ decreases (to 63.85%). On the other hand, looking at Panel C in Figure 3, the speciation of all the surface ammonia species for the NH₃ + 34% H₂O case (fraction of each peak area compared to the total ammonia peak areas) is the most similar to the speciation of surface ammonia species for the NH₃-only case. In other words, the impact of 34% H₂O addition has the most minimal impact on ammonia adsorption in terms of speciation, while the other cases result in a significant change in the speciation, in other words, the distribution of the ammonia species being different. In addition to the surface speciation not being significantly impacted, the 34% H₂O case, which represents the

flue gas of 100% H₂, also exhibited higher NO_x conversion in the previous SCR experiments in the presence of SO₂ compared to 100% CH₄ where the H₂O content was 19%.

Furthermore, when comparing the results obtained with different levels of water, the following observations can be made. When increasing the water content from 10% H₂O to 20% H₂O, protonated ammonia increases. In contrast, going from 20% H₂O to 34% H₂O decreases protonated ammonia, suggesting that a non-monotonic behavior is observed with respect to the water concentration, similar to the behavior of the fresh catalyst, which aligns with the NO_x conversion trend observed in the previous SCR experiments as mentioned above. The increase in the Brønsted acid sites for 20% H₂O also results in NH₃ adsorbing right away while there is a delay for 10% and 34% H₂O, meaning NH₃ is competing with H₂O for sites for these cases, when comparing the time-resolved spectra (Figures 24S-26S).

The combined presence of O₂ and H₂O significantly alters NH₃ adsorption behavior, with effects that are dependent on water concentration. For the fresh catalyst, comparison of NH₃ + 10% H₂O and NH₃ + 10% H₂O + 10 O₂ (Panels A and B in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$, shows that the addition of O₂ leads to a sharp drop in coordinated NH₃ species (from 41.94% to 19.98%) and a notable increase in protonated ammonia (from 58.06% to 80.02%) at almost all related peaks of NH₄⁺. The same trend is also observed when comparing NH₃ + 10% H₂O + 10 O₂ to NH₃ only. However, when comparing NH₃ + 20% H₂O and NH₃ + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ (Panels A and B in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$, the addition of O₂ causes a minimal change in speciation, and both NH₄⁺ and coordinated NH₃ remain nearly constant. The speciation is also similar when comparing NH₃ + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ to NH₃ only, but there is a slight increase in protonated ammonia compared to NH₃ only. To evaluate the effect of water, comparison of NH₃ + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ and NH₃ + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ to NH₃ + 10% O₂ illustrates that the addition of water results in an increase in protonated ammonia. This suggests that water in the presence of O₂ promotes Brønsted acidity, displacing coordinated NH₃ and stabilizing NH₄⁺ ions, with the effect being more pronounced at 10% H₂O than 20% H₂O. Furthermore, when comparing the time-resolved spectra, despite the delay that was observed in NH₃ adsorption in the presence of H₂O, the NH₃ peaks start developing faster when O₂ is added (Figure 6S for NH₃ + 10% O₂ + 10% H₂O and Figure 7S for NH₃ + 10% O₂ + 20% H₂O). Even though H₂O occupies available sites, O₂ can reoxidize the reduced V⁴⁺ sites to V⁵⁺ and create new sites for NH₃ to adsorb. These results

suggest that under lean conditions where O_2 is in excess, the oxidative environment can facilitate the restoration of acid sites for NH_3 to adsorb. In parallel to this, higher NO_x conversion was observed in the previous SCR experiments for the lean cases where there is 10% O_2 ($\Phi = 0.5$) compared to the near-stoichiometric cases ($\Phi = 0.98$) with minimal O_2 .

For the used catalyst, when comparing $NH_3 + 10\% H_2O$ and $NH_3 + 10\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ (Panels C and D in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% CH_4 with $\Phi = 0.5$, a trend similar to that of the fresh catalyst is observed, where O_2 addition suppresses coordinated NH_3 (from 26.24% to 19.78%) and increases protonated ammonia (to 80.22%), with a strong boost at 1427cm^{-1} . The same trend is also observed when comparing $NH_3 + 10\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ to NH_3 only. The distribution between coordinated vs. protonated ammonia is the same for both the fresh and used catalysts. On the other hand, when comparing $NH_3 + 20\% H_2O$ and $NH_3 + 20\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ (Panels C and D in Figure 3), which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.5$, the trend reverses: when O_2 is added, coordinated NH_3 increases significantly (from 13.25 % to 30.94%) and protonated ammonia decreases (from 86.75% to 69.06%), yielding the same speciation observed for the NH_3 -only case. The impact of 20% H_2O that caused the coordinated ammonia to decrease (compared to NH_3 only) is reversed when O_2 is added. For both the used and fresh catalysts, the distribution between coordinated vs. protonated ammonia for the $NH_3 + 20\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ case is similar to the speciation of NH_3 only. In addition, comparison of $NH_3 + 10\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ and $NH_3 + 20\% H_2O + 10\% O_2$ to $NH_3 + 10\% O_2$ illustrates that the addition of water results in an increase in protonated ammonia, with the effect being more pronounced at 10% H_2O than 20% H_2O , similar to the behavior observed for the fresh catalyst.

Furthermore, when comparing the time-resolved spectra, NH_3 peaks start developing faster when O_2 is added (Figure 27S for $NH_3 + 10\% O_2 + 10\% H_2O$) compared to the delay observed for 10% H_2O only (Figure 24S). Similar to the behavior observed for the fresh catalyst, these results suggest that under lean conditions where O_2 is in excess, the oxidative environment can facilitate the restoration of acid sites for NH_3 to adsorb.

For the NH_3 only experiments, when evaluating the effect of water on the adsorbed ammonia species for the fresh catalyst vs. the used catalyst, a similar trend is observed for all the water concentrations tested (10%, 20% and 34%) as well as the cases that includes water and O_2 (10%

H₂O + 10%O₂ and 20%H₂O + 10% O₂). For all the cases tested with water, more protonated ammonia species are observed on the used catalyst samples. In other words, the used catalyst has more Brønsted sites than the fresh catalyst, consistently for all the cases. Since the used catalyst were exposed to SO₂, this behavior could be due to the formation of sulfur species on the surface [15] that have been shown to become strong Brønsted acid sites in the presence of H₂O [38].

3.2 Experiments with NO

This section investigates how NO adsorbs onto the catalyst surface under varying conditions, including its individual adsorption, and interactions in the presence of O₂ and/or water vapor at different concentrations (10%, 20%, and 34%). The results provide detailed insight into the interplay between NO, O₂, and H₂O in shaping adsorption behavior, with implications for NO activation and surface reaction mechanisms central to SCR performance and catalyst durability.

Figure 4 presents in-situ DRIFTS spectra illustrating NO adsorption behavior on V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under varying gas compositions. Panels A-C correspond to the fresh catalyst, while panels D-F show results for the used catalyst. Full-range spectra (4000-1200 cm⁻¹) are shown in A and D, high-wavenumber regions (3700-3100 cm⁻¹) are highlighted in B and E, and low-wavenumber regions (1800-1200 cm⁻¹) are shown in C and F. In spectrum (a) presented in Figure 4 (A and D for the fresh catalyst and used catalyst, respectively), the first region, between 1200-1800 cm⁻¹, exhibits peaks associated with adsorbed NO species, and the second region corresponds to hydroxyl (-OH) vibrations, attributed to isolated OH groups and surface OH species. Five noticeable positive peaks appear in the low wavenumber region, providing insights into the adsorption and transformation of NO_x species on the catalyst surface. The first positive peak corresponds to the bridging NO adsorption at 1620 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of NO molecules interacting with surface sites [39, 40]. The second positive peak at 1600 cm⁻¹ is attributed to bidentate nitrates (NO₃⁻), highlighting their formation through strong coordination with the catalyst surface [39, 40]. Peaks three and four, observed at 1378 cm⁻¹ and 1320 cm⁻¹ [39], are associated with monodentate nitrates (NO₃⁻) and nitrites (NO₂⁻), respectively. The fifth positive peak at 1250 cm⁻¹ [41] corresponds to nitrites (NO₂⁻), further confirming the diversity of nitrate and nitrite species present on the surface. These findings emphasize the complex interactions of NO_x species with the catalyst, involving multiple adsorption modes and the formation of surface intermediates that play key roles in catalytic processes. In addition, hydroxyl peaks are observed in the high

wavenumber region between $\sim 3200\text{-}3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [42]. Surface hydroxyl groups play a critical role in adsorption processes and can exist in distinct environments, which are identifiable through their vibrational characteristics in the IR spectrum. Hydrogen-bonded hydroxyls typically exhibit broad peaks in the $\sim 3200\text{-}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range due to strong intermolecular interactions [43]. In contrast, isolated terminal hydroxyl groups display sharp and distinct peaks at higher wavenumbers, around $\sim 3700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, reflecting their weakly interacting and more localized nature [42]. The presence and relative intensities of these peaks depend on the specific composition and distribution of hydroxyl groups on the catalyst surface. For vanadium oxides, it is common to observe both types of hydroxyl groups, given the diversity of surface sites [44].

Figure 4: In-situ DRIFT spectra of NO on fresh (A-C) and used (D-F) V_2O_5 - WO_3 / TiO_2 catalysts under varying gas compositions. Panels A and D: full-range spectra (4000-1200 cm^{-1}); B and E: high-wavenumber region (3700-3100 cm^{-1}); C and F: low-wavenumber region (1800-1200 cm^{-1}). Figure 5 presents the quantitative DRIFTS analysis of NO adsorption on fresh (Panels A and B) and used (Panels C and D) V_2O_5 - WO_3 / TiO_2 catalysts under various gas compositions. In order to evaluate the distribution of different surface species under different environments, areas under the peaks for each spectrum shown in Figure 4 were integrated to be able to quantitatively compare how the distribution of peak associated with different surface species is changing as a result of the

presence of O₂ and/or H₂O. In Panels A and C, integrated peak areas were calculated for the characteristic vibrational bands corresponding to nitrate and nitrite species across low wavenumber regions and each peak area was divided by the total area of all peaks, representing the percentage of each surface species among others. Panels B and D summarize the total contributions of these integrated peaks, categorized into different nitrate and nitrite species, and expressed as percentages of the total NO-related signal. This analysis enables comparison of NO adsorption modes and speciation between fresh and used catalyst surfaces under different conditions.

Figure 5: Integrated DRIFTS peak areas for NO adsorption on fresh (A and B) and used (C and D) V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under varying gas compositions at 250 °C. Panels A and C display integrations from the low wavenumber regions. Panels B and D summarize the total integrated intensities of different nitrate and nitrite species.

A direct comparison between NO adsorption on the fresh and used catalysts reveals significant differences in surface speciation. On the fresh catalyst (Panels A and B in Figure 5), the adsorption profile is more diverse: nitrate species (NO_3^-) account for 44.97%, nitrite species (NO_2^-) for 23.45%, and bridging NO for 31.58%. This balanced distribution suggests active participation of both nitrate and nitrite pathways on a well-preserved surface. In contrast, the used catalyst (Panels C and D in Figure 5) shows a marked shift toward bridging NO (1620 cm^{-1}) dominance (54.12%), and the overall nitrite species dropping sharply (peak at 1320 cm^{-1} dropping to 3.00% and the peak at 1250 cm^{-1} disappearing) and the nitrate species dropping slightly to 42.82%. The suppression of nitrite bands and enrichment of NO on the used catalyst indicate that surface modifications from prior SCR exposure favors less oxidized NO_x species on the surface.

The addition of O_2 significantly alters NO adsorption speciation on both fresh and used catalysts. On the fresh catalyst, comparing NO and NO + 10% O_2 (Panels A and B in Figure 5) shows that O_2 addition leads to a considerable increase in bridging NO (53.90%) while the nitrate (33.09%) and nitrite species (13.01%) decrease. In addition, O_2 promotes the formation of bidentate nitrate (1600 cm^{-1}) while monodentate nitrate (1378 cm^{-1}) decreases, with the total nitrate species decreasing compared to NO only. Similarly, on the used catalyst, comparing NO and NO + 10% O_2 (Panels C and D in Figure 5), O_2 addition leads to a moderate increase in bridging NO (up to 62.68%) and a decrease in monodentate nitrate (to 34%) is observed. While the bidentate nitrate peak at 1600 cm^{-1} and the nitrate peak at 1250 cm^{-1} are observed for the fresh catalyst, they are not present for the used catalyst.

The impact of water vapor on NO adsorption is strongly dependent on the water concentration. On the fresh catalyst (Panels A and B in Figure 5), comparing NO and NO + 10% H_2O shows that introducing 10% H_2O increases bridging NO to 39.30% while monodentate nitrate slightly decreases to 39.14%, with the bidentate nitrate remaining absent. Nitrite peak at 1320 cm^{-1} shows a notable rise (9.95%), while the nitrite peak at 1250 cm^{-1} decreases (11.61%) with the overall amount of nitrites decreasing compared to NO only. At higher water levels, i.e., 20% H_2O , representing the flue gas environment for 100% CH_4 with $\Phi = 0.98$, and 34% H_2O , representing the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.98$, NO adsorption is fully suppressed with no detectable peaks, suggesting that excessive water content inhibits NO adsorption. For these cases where NO adsorption is suppressed, the SCR reaction cannot take place via the Langmuir

Hinshelwood mechanism and the reaction should involve NO in the gas phase via the Eley-Rideal mechanism.

On the used catalyst, (Panels C and D in Figure 5), comparing NO and NO + 10% H₂O demonstrates that adding 10% H₂O shifts the adsorption profile toward dominant monodentate nitrate (54.37%), accompanied by declines in bridging NO (44.39%) and nitrite (1.24%) species. For the fresh catalyst, an opposite behavior was observed where the presence of 10% H₂O increased the bridging NO and decreased the nitrate peak. However, a similar behavior is observed for the fresh and used catalysts for higher water content. Higher water levels (20% and 34% H₂O, representing the flue gas environments of 100% CH₄ and 100% H₂, respectively, with $\Phi = 0.98$) completely suppress NO adsorption on the used catalyst, reinforcing the conclusion that excessive water coverage deactivates or outcompetes NO for adsorption sites. Again, for these cases, the possibility of the Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism is ruled out.

The combined effect of O₂ and H₂O on NO adsorption reveals a change in the surface species on both fresh and used catalysts. For the fresh catalyst, a comparison of NO + 10% H₂O and NO + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂, reveals that adding 10% O₂ in the presence of 10% H₂O, which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$, shifts adsorption toward more oxidized nitrate forms (64.17%), notably enhancing monodentate (1378 cm⁻¹) and bidentate (1600 cm⁻¹) nitrates while suppressing nitrite species at 1250 cm⁻¹. Bridging NO slightly decreases (25.93%), suggesting surface reorganization under oxidizing, hydrated conditions. Similar changes are also observed compared to the NO-only case. When comparing NO and NO + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂, which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$, bridging NO becomes the dominant species (83.83%), bidentate nitrate rises to 16.17%, and all other nitrate and nitrite peaks vanish. This shift indicates that under high water content and oxidizing conditions, the surface becomes structurally simplified, dominated by strongly bound bridging NO. Comparing to the NO + 20% H₂O case, where all NO peaks were suppressed, the addition of 10% O₂ in the presence of 20% H₂O restores the activity in terms of NO adsorption.

On the used catalyst, the addition of 10% O₂ in the presence of 10% H₂O, which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$, produces no detectable NO adsorption signals, indicating that lower water content under oxidizing conditions is insufficient to restore surface activity in terms of NO adsorption for the catalyst that was previously exposed to the SCR

environment. However, for $\text{NO} + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O} + 10\% \text{O}_2$, which is representative of the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.5$, a clear reactivation effect is observed compared to $\text{NO} + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ where the NO peaks were suppressed: bridging NO becomes the dominant species (69.32%), similar to the fresh catalyst, monodentate nitrate peak at 1378 cm^{-1} emerges (17.33%), and nitrite peak at 1320 cm^{-1} reappears (13.35%). Similar to the fresh catalyst, O_2 in combination with higher water content can partially regenerate active sites and allow NO to adsorb on the surface.

Furthermore, another observation that can be made when comparing NO adsorption on the fresh and used catalysts is that the used catalyst was priorly exposed to the SCR environment and already has NH_3 that is pre-adsorbed on the catalyst surface. When NO is introduced into the used catalyst, it will likely react with the pre-adsorbed NH_3 species on the surface. This can be confirmed from the positive OH band observed around 3600 cm^{-1} for the cases where NO peaks are not suppressed (NO , $\text{NO} + \text{O}_2$ and $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$). This band was negative for the NH_3 adsorption case as a result of NH_3 binding to the Brønsted acid site. If the time-resolved spectra for NO adsorption on the used catalyst (provided in Appendix, Figure 29S) is evaluated, no NO peaks are observed for the first 30 minutes, after which peaks related to NO adsorption develop along with the positive OH band around 3600 cm^{-1} . Based on this, it can be speculated that the surface sites are saturated with NH_3 in the beginning competing with NO adsorption. When NO is introduced, it likely reacts with the NH_3 species on the Brønsted acid sites and after a while sites become available for NO to adsorb on the surface and the OH band emerges as the Brønsted sites become available after depletion of the surface NH_3 species. When the time-resolved spectra for $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2$ on the used catalyst (provided in Appendix, Figure 30S) is evaluated, positive OH band is also observed confirming the depletion of surface NH_3 species on the Brønsted sites; however, the difference compared to NO only is that the peaks develop within the first 5 minutes as opposed to the NO-only case where the peaks start developing after 30 minutes. It can be speculated that the presence of O_2 speeds up the reaction while for the NO-only case, the reaction is relying only on the surface oxygen. The presence of gas-phase O_2 is known to increase the reaction rate for the SCR reaction and reoxidize the vanadia and replenish the sites. The same behavior can also be observed when comparing the time-resolved spectra of $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Figure 31S) and $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Figure 35S) where the peaks start developing after 20 minutes for $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ while the

peaks develop within the first 5 minutes for $\text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ due to the presence of gas-phase O_2 .

3.3 Experiments with NO and NH_3

This section systematically explores the co-adsorption behavior of NH_3 and NO on fresh and used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts under controlled conditions to mimic real SCR environments. It examines four key scenarios: (1) NH_3 and NO adsorption without other gases to understand their fundamental surface interactions, (2) NH_3 , NO and O_2 adsorption to evaluate the influence of oxygen, (3) NH_3 and NO with varying H_2O vapor levels (10%, 20%, 34%) to assess the role of H_2O vapor and site competition, and (4) NH_3 , NO and O_2 with H_2O to study the combined effects of oxidation and water vapor under realistic flue gas conditions.

Figure 6 presents the in-situ DRIFTS spectra of NH_3 and NO on $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts under different gas compositions. Panels A-C show the results for the fresh catalyst, while panels D-F display the spectra for the used catalyst samples. Full-range spectra ($4000\text{-}1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) are shown in panels A and D, providing an overview of all relevant vibrational modes. Panels B and E focus on the high-wavenumber region ($3700\text{-}3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) while the panels C and F focus on the low-wavenumber region ($1800\text{-}1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Before delving into the details of the results, it is important to note that there is a noticeable peak overlap in the $1700\text{-}1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, which corresponds to intermediates formed during NH_3 and NO adsorption. However, peaks that were observed are predominantly related to NH_3 adsorption species, especially checking the pattern in spectrum (a) in Figure 6 ($\text{NO} + \text{NH}_3$) and comparing with spectrum (a) in Figure 2 (NH_3 only). In the competitive adsorption of NO and NH_3 on vanadium oxide, the dominant species is influenced by multiple factors, ultimately favoring NH_3 adsorption under most conditions. The affinity of the surface plays a crucial role, as NH_3 , being a basic molecule, exhibits a strong interaction with the acidic sites of vanadium oxide [45]. This affinity allows NH_3 to bind more readily compared to NO [45]. Additionally, partial pressures impact the competition, where NH_3 prevails when NH_3 concentration is higher, while NO dominates only at elevated NO partial pressures [1]. Temperature effects further differentiate the adsorption behavior such that NO adsorption is favored at elevated temperatures due to its thermal stability, whereas NH_3 adsorption weakens. However, in the SCR process, NH_3 typically dominates as it serves as the reductant for NO , forming the basis of the reaction mechanism [46]. These factors collectively support the observed

dominant NH_3 adsorption on vanadium oxide surfaces. Thus, the peaks observed in the spectra of the $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ experiments can be primarily attributed to NH_3 species.

Figure 6: In-situ DRIFT spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ on fresh (A-C) and used (D-F) $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts under varying gas compositions. Panels A and D: full-range spectra (4000-1200 cm^{-1}); B and E: high-wavenumber region (3700-3100 cm^{-1}); C and F: low-wavenumber region (1800-1200 cm^{-1}).

Figure 7 presents the quantitative DRIFTS analysis of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ on fresh (Panels A and B) and used (Panels C and D) $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalysts under varying gas compositions. In order to

evaluate the distribution of different surface species under different environments, areas under the peaks for each spectrum shown in Figure 6 were integrated to be able to quantitatively compare how the distribution of peaks associated with different surface species is changing as a result of the presence of O₂ and/or H₂O. In Panels A and C, integrated peak areas were calculated for the characteristic vibrational bands associated with coordinated NH₃ and protonated NH₄⁺ species across both high and low wavenumber regions and each peak area was divided by the total area of all peaks, representing the percentage of each surface species among others. Panels B and D summarize the total contributions of coordinated versus protonated ammonia species, expressed as percentages of the total NH₃-related signal.

Figure 7: Quantitative analysis of integrated DRIFTS peak areas for NH₃ and NO co-adsorption and related species adsorbed on fresh (A and B) and used (C and D) V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalysts under varying gas compositions and humidity levels at 250 °C. Panels A and C display integrations

from the high and low wavenumber regions. Panels B and D summarize the total integrated intensities of coordinated (L-NH₃) versus protonated ammonia (B-NH₄⁺).

Before analyzing the results of NH₃ + NO experiments, it is worth mentioning that while similar peaks are observed for NH₃ and NH₃ + NO cases due to NH₃ peaks dominating the spectra, different behaviors regarding the influence of O₂ and H₂O can be observed when comparing the two cases. When evaluating the results of NH₃ + NO with O₂ and/or H₂O, the picture gets complicated due to the SCR reaction taking place, which results in the formation of H₂O as a product and reduction of the vanadium sites, both affecting the distribution of the surface NH₃ species, making it difficult to deconvolute the impact of these factors. In addition, when evaluating the time-resolved spectra for NH₃ + NO cases, a more transient behavior is observed in the beginning due to the reaction taking place, but eventually the surface species reach steady state. Since detailed transient experiments were not conducted in this study, only the steady-state data will be interpreted here.

When the NH₃ + NO mixture is introduced to the fresh catalyst (Panels A and B in Figure 7), adsorbed NH₃ species show a balanced distribution of Lewis and Brønsted acid sites with 34.85% coordinated ammonia and 65.15% protonated ammonia, similar to the NH₃-only adsorption on the fresh catalyst. By comparing the NH₃ + NO spectra for the fresh and used catalysts (Panels A and C in Figure 7), it becomes evident that ammonia-related signals exhibit greater diversity on the used catalyst surface, similar to the NH₃-only case; however, the overall fractions of coordinated vs. protonated ammonia are similar for the fresh and used catalysts, with a slight increase in coordinated ammonia for the used catalyst. While the overall fraction of the total protonated ammonia species on the surface does not change significantly, there is a pronounced decrease in the intensity of the Brønsted-associated band at 1427 cm⁻¹ accompanied by an increase of 3261 and 1684 cm⁻¹, similar to the NH₃-only case.

The influence of addition of 10% O₂ (representing the O₂ content of the flue gas stream with $\Phi = 0.5$) into NH₃ + NO was evaluated for both fresh and used catalysts. For the fresh catalyst, comparing the spectra of NH₃ + NO and NH₃ + NO + 10% O₂ (Panels A and B in Figure 7) reveals that the total coordinated NH₃ decreases from 34.85% to 27.77% with the addition of O₂, particularly at 3377 and 1250 cm⁻¹. In addition, a slight increase at 1339 cm⁻¹ suggests redistribution of coordinated NH₃ species. On the other hand, protonated ammonia increases largely driven by a strong rise at 1684 cm⁻¹, reflecting enhanced Brønsted acidity under oxidizing

conditions. Partial transformation of Lewis sites to Brønsted sites can occur as the reduced catalyst is oxidized upon exposure to oxygen [18]. In contrast, for the NH_3 -only adsorption case, adding O_2 to NH_3 did not make a change in the distribution of acid sites on the fresh catalyst; in other words, the ratio of NH_4^+ to coordinated NH_3 was the same for the cases of NH_3 and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{O}_2$. However, the situation is different when NO is included in the gas mixture, turning the environment into the SCR environment. For the cases of NH_3 and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{O}_2$, only adsorption is taking place and the effect of O_2 on NH_3 adsorption can be observed clearly. However, for $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$, the catalyst is being reduced as a result of the SCR reaction and adding O_2 reoxidizes the reduced sites, resulting in a different behavior than the addition of O_2 into NH_3 only.

For the used catalyst, when comparing the spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2$ in Figure 7 Panels C and D, coordinated ammonia drops from 37.32% to 25.48%, while protonated ammonia increases, similar to the behavior observed for the fresh catalyst. While a similar increase in protonated ammonia is observed, there is a significant increase at 1427 cm^{-1} for the used catalyst, that was not observed for the fresh catalyst. From the coordinated ammonia species, the 1339 cm^{-1} band increases slightly, suggesting selective retention of certain NH_3 configurations, which was also observed on the surface of the fresh catalyst. Overall, O_2 shifts NH_3 adsorption from Lewis to Brønsted acid sites on both catalysts, but the shift is stronger on the used sample. This behavior is contrary to what was observed when adding O_2 to NH_3 only. On both the fresh and used catalysts, the ratio of the protonated ammonia to coordinated ammonia, in other words, the ratio of Brønsted acid sites to Lewis acid sites, is higher for the $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + \text{O}_2$ case than that for the $\text{NH}_3 + \text{O}_2$ case. A similar behavior was observed by Song et al. [37] for a $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst, where they attributed this to be either due to the water generated from the reaction hydrating the catalyst surface and shifting the equilibrium of Brønsted to Lewis ratio or due to the differences in the oxidation states of the catalysts. They concluded that the change is likely due to the change in the oxidation state, since the water that is produced during reaction is very little.

The influence of water vapor on $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ adsorption/reaction reveals distinct trends between fresh and used catalysts, shaped by both the water level and surface condition. On the fresh catalyst, by comparing $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panels A and B in Figure 7), adding 10% H_2O causes a moderate decrease in coordinated NH_3 from 34.85% to 31.67%, especially at 1339 , 1250 and 3377 cm^{-1} , while the protonated ammonia increases from 65.15% to 68.33%, marked by a sharp increase at 1684 cm^{-1} along with a decrease at 1427 cm^{-1} , indicating a shift

toward Brønsted acidity. Interestingly, the 1600 cm^{-1} coordinated NH_3 band increases suggesting selective stabilization of certain NH_3 modes. At 20% H_2O , simulating the flue gas environment for 100% CH_4 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, coordinated NH_3 drops sharply to 20%, particularly at 1339 , 3154 and 3377 cm^{-1} , while protonated ammonia increases to 80%, mostly at 1427 and 1684 cm^{-1} , confirming a strong water-induced transition from Lewis to Brønsted adsorption. At 34% H_2O , simulating the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, there is not much change compared to $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$, just a slight increase in coordinated NH_3 and a slight decrease in NH_4^+ . When comparing the results obtained with different levels of water, the same behavior of the NH_3 -only case is observed where increasing the H_2O content from 10% to 20% increases protonated ammonia while going from 20% to 34% H_2O decreases protonated ammonia, suggesting a non-monotonic behavior. As mentioned earlier, this behavior is in-line with the non-monotonic change in NO_x conversion observed when increasing the H_2O content from 19% to 34% in the previous SCR experiments.

For the used catalyst, comparison of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Panels C and D in Figure 7) shows that coordinated ammonia drops from 37.32% to 30.99% and protonated ammonia rises. Similarly, at 20% H_2O , simulating the flue gas environment for 100% CH_4 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, coordinated ammonia decreases to 31.01% while protonated ammonia increases. For both 10 and 20% H_2O , the rise in NH_4^+ occurs as a result of a large gain at 1427 cm^{-1} indicating strong NH_4^+ stabilization while 1684 cm^{-1} decreases redistributing NH_4^+ . Notably, the 1339 cm^{-1} band increases while the total coordinated NH_3 goes down, pointing to selective retention or reorganization of Lewis-bound NH_3 . Similarly, at 34% H_2O , simulating the flue gas environment for 100% H_2 with $\Phi = 0.98$ where the O_2 content is negligible, the coordinated ammonia signal drops slightly (to 35.03%) while protonated ammonia slightly rises. Consistent with the literature, there is a shift toward Brønsted species in the presence of water, with the shift being larger at lower water content (10 and 20%) and less at higher water content (34%), making the speciation of ammonia compounds on the surface with $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 34\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ similar to that of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ without the water presence. This is also true for the NH_3 -only case where there is less Brønsted acid sites for 34% H_2O compared to 20% H_2O . For both NH_3 and $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$, 34% H_2O addition results in minimal change in surface speciation of the used catalyst compared to without the presence of H_2O . As mentioned earlier, in addition to the surface speciation not being significantly impacted, the 34% H_2O case, which represents the flue gas of

100% H₂, also exhibited higher NO_x conversion in the previous SCR experiments [ref] in the presence of SO₂ compared to 100% CH₄ where the H₂O content was 19%. In terms of the sulfur speciation on the catalyst surface based on XPS analysis, the 20% H₂O case resulted in SO₃ formation on the catalyst surface while the 34% H₂O case had mostly SO₄ formation in addition to SO₃.

For the fresh catalyst, comparing NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O with NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂, simulating the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$, (Panels A and B in Figure 7) shows that O₂ addition in the presence of 10% H₂O causes a decrease in coordinated ammonia (from 31.67% to 20.80) and an increase in protonated ammonia, similar to the NH₃-only case. The same trend is observed when comparing NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ to NH₃ + NO where the addition of 10% O₂ and 10% H₂O results in a decrease in coordinated ammonia. At 20% H₂O, comparing NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O with NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂, simulating the flue gas environment for 100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$, shows that adding O₂ causes a slight increase in coordinated ammonia (from 20.01% to 22.04%), while protonated ammonia decreases slightly. For 20% H₂O, while O₂ slightly shifts surface preference toward Lewis acid site coordination, the fraction of Brønsted acid sites in the presence of O₂ and H₂O together is still much higher compared to NH₃ + NO, similar to the behavior observed for NH₃ adsorption. To evaluate the effect of water, comparison of NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ and NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ to NH₃ + NO + 10% O₂ illustrates that the addition of water results in an increase in protonated ammonia. This suggests that water in the presence of O₂ promotes Brønsted acidity with the effect being slightly more pronounced at 10% H₂O than 20% H₂O, similar to the NH₃-only case. In terms of NO_x conversion that was observed in the previous SCR experiments [ref], addition of 10% O₂ resulted in an increase in NO_x conversion for both 100% CH₄ (10% H₂O) and 100% H₂ (20% H₂O), with a higher increase for 20% H₂O, while the Brønsted acid sites increased for 10% H₂O and slightly decreased for 20% H₂O with the addition of 10% O₂. When comparing different levels of H₂O, going from 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ (100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$) to 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ (100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$) results in a decrease in Brønsted acid sites, corresponding to an increase in NO_x conversion.

For the used catalyst (Panels C and D in Figure 7), comparing NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O with NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O + 10% O₂, simulating the flue gas environment for 100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$, shows that adding O₂ in the presence of 10% H₂O decreases coordinated ammonia from 30.99% to

25.51% while increasing protonated ammonia. At 20% H₂O, when comparing NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O with NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O + 10% O₂, simulating the flue gas environment for 100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$, coordinated ammonia decreases from 31.01% to 28.20%, and protonated ammonia rises. For both cases (10 and 20% H₂O), while the addition of O₂ shifts the surface preference toward Brønsted protonation compared to NH₃ + NO + H₂O, the fraction of Brønsted acid sites in the presence of O₂ and H₂O is also higher compared to NH₃ + NO, similar to the behavior of the fresh catalyst. The addition of O₂ and H₂O together resulted in an increase in Brønsted acid sites for the NH₃ adsorption case on both fresh and used catalysts as well. In terms of NO_x conversion that was observed in the previous SCR experiments [ref], in the presence of SO₂, addition of 10% O₂ resulted in a decrease in NO_x conversion for both 100% CH₄ and 100% H₂. Comparing different levels of H₂O, going from 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ (100% CH₄ with $\Phi = 0.5$) to 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ (100% H₂ with $\Phi = 0.5$) results in a decrease in Brønsted acid sites, corresponding to an increase in NO_x conversion, similar to the fresh catalyst behavior. In terms of the sulfur speciation on the catalyst surface based on XPS analysis, the 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ case resulted in SO₃ formation on the catalyst surface while the 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ case had SO₄ formation in addition to SO₃.

4. Conclusions

This study provided quantitative insights into the impact of hydrogen blending, i.e., higher water vapor, and SO₂ exposure on the performance of V₂O₅–WO₃/TiO₂ SCR catalysts. Effects of flue gas species, water, O₂ and SO₂, on the adsorption of NH₃ and NO as well as the SCR reaction have been studied under industrially relevant conditions representing the flue gas of natural gas and blends of natural gas and hydrogen. The results demonstrated that the SCR activity is closely linked to the nature of ammonia species on the catalyst surface. Comparing all the experiments performed at different conditions highlight the fact that the distribution of the surface ammonia species is very dynamic and strongly depends on the reaction environment, especially the presence of water vapor with the population of surface species changing with the water content. The presence of SO₂ and H₂O and their interactions also significantly impact the population of surface ammonia species and the SCR activity.

The DRIFTS results obtained in this study sheds light into the previous observations in terms of the change in NO_x conversion under different conditions. In the previous study, the authors have shown the impact of equivalence ratio, in other words, the presence of excess O₂, water

concentration in the flue gas and the presence of SO₂ on SCR activity. Combining the previous NO_x conversion and catalyst characterization results with the in situ DRIFTS results here provides a clear picture of the influence of hydrogen blending on catalyst activity and sulfur poisoning.

In the previous SCR experiments, increasing the amount of excess O₂ ($\Phi = 0.98 \rightarrow \Phi = 0.5$) in the presence of SO₂ resulted in a decrease in NO_x conversion for both 100% CH₄ and 100% H₂. For 100% CH₄, changing Φ from 0.98 to 0.5 changes the composition from 20% H₂O to 10% H₂O + 10% O₂. DRIFTS results reveal that 20% H₂O has less Bronsted acid sites than 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ on the used catalyst exposed to SO₂. For 100% H₂, changing Φ from 0.98 to 0.5 changes the composition from 34% H₂O to 20% H₂O + 10% O₂. DRIFTS results reveal that 34% H₂O has less Bronsted acid sites than 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ on the used catalyst exposed to SO₂. For both cases, the decrease in conversion corresponds to an increase in Bronsted acid sites.

In the previous SCR experiments, increasing the H₂ content in the fuel (100% CH₄ \rightarrow 100% H₂) in other words, increasing the H₂O content in the flue gas resulted in an increase in NO_x conversion in the presence of SO₂ for both 100% CH₄ and 100% H₂ and improved the sulfur resistance of the catalyst. Comparing the two near-stoichiometric cases with $\Phi = 0.98$, 100% CH₄ case with 20% H₂O had SO₃ on the surface and lower conversion compared to 100% H₂ case with 34% H₂O where mostly SO₄ was observed on the surface with a less SO₃. DRIFTS results reveal that the 20% H₂O case has more Brønsted acid sites than the 34% H₂O case. Comparing the two lean cases with $\Phi = 0.5$, 100% CH₄ case with 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ had SO₃ on the surface and lower conversion compared to 100% H₂ case with 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ where SO₄ on the surface was observed in addition to SO₃. DRIFTS results reveal that the 10% H₂O + 10% O₂ case has more Brønsted acid sites than the 20% H₂O + 10% O₂ case. Therefore, for both equivalence ratios ($\Phi = 0.98$ and $\Phi = 0.5$), the SO₂-exposed used catalyst samples that exhibited higher conversion had less Brønsted acid sites than the samples that exhibited lower conversion.

Overall, both Phase I and Phase II of this study have demonstrated that SCR systems can continue to operate effectively without modification when transitioning to hydrogen–natural gas fuel blends, offering a promising route for decarbonizing stationary power systems without compromising NO_x control performance. The observed resilience under high water and sulfur conditions positions SCR as a robust NO_x control strategy in future hydrogen-integrated stationary power systems.

Appendix

Figure 1S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH_3 adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 2S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{O}_2$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 3S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 4S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + 20% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 5S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 34\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 6S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + 10% O₂ + 10% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 7S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 8S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 9S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 10S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 11S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 20% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 12S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 34% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 13S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ + 10% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 14S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ + 20% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 15S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 16S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO + 10% O₂ adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 17S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 18S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 19S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO + 34% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 20S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the fresh $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 21S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO + 10% O₂ + 20% H₂O adsorption on the fresh V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 22S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH_3 adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 23S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{O}_2$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 24S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 25S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH_3 + 20% H_2O adsorption on the used V_2O_5 - WO_3/TiO_2 catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 26S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + 34% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 27S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + 10% O₂ + 10% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 28S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + 10% O₂ + 20% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 29S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO adsorption on the used $V_2O_5-WO_3/TiO_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 30S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 31S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 32S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 20% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 33S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 34% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 34S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ + 10% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 35S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NO + 10% O₂ + 20% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 36S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 37S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 38S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO + 10% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 39S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of NH₃ + NO + 20% H₂O adsorption on the used V₂O₅-WO₃/TiO₂ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 40S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 34\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 41S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 10\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

Figure 42S: Time-resolved DRIFTS spectra of $\text{NH}_3 + \text{NO} + 10\% \text{O}_2 + 20\% \text{H}_2\text{O}$ adsorption on the used $\text{V}_2\text{O}_5\text{-WO}_3/\text{TiO}_2$ catalyst surface over a 2-hour period.

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